

D6.4 Maximising impact report

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2. Executive Summary

In this deliverable, you will find a detailed explanation of the impact achieved within the Möbius Communication Plan (D6.1) throughout the three years of the project. This report highlights the communication strategies, stakeholder engagement initiatives, and tools and channels used to disseminate information effectively. It includes the website creation and management, videos; blog articles; marketing materials designed to generate engagement during the project's event attendance; social media channels implemented and their impact on the audience; newsletter strategy and impact, and scientific articles published in addition to open access data uploaded on Zenodo.

To maximize the impact of these activities, this deliverable also collects the exploitation roadmaps elaborated for the project's different Key Exploitable Results (KERs). Built upon D6.2, the Möbius exploitation methodology explained in that deliverable has been applied and the exploitable results have been updated and validated within the consortium. Domains such as the market strategy, market positioning and IPR elements for the main KERs are collected in the document.

This document also includes monitoring and evaluation processes, as well as emphasising the importance of ongoing assessment throughout the project. By closely monitoring progress and regularly reviewing outcomes, FMWC ensured that the communication plan was consistently aligned with the project goals and allowed for timely adjustments.

This document serves as a project review and contains valuable insights and proven best practices derived from Möbius's experience. These insights provide a practical guide for future projects, offering 'best practice' advice based on lessons learned and challenges overcome. Using these insights, project teams can approach similar endeavours more confidently and efficiently, contributing to project growth and success, and ensuring the replication and exploitation of the results of Möbius and other similar projects.

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6. Terminology and Acronyms

<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>EUT</i>	<i>Eurecat</i>
<i>FEP</i>	<i>Federation of European Publishers</i>
<i>FMWC</i>	<i>Mobile World Capital Barcelona</i>
<i>FP</i>	<i>Framework Programme</i>
<i>KKW</i>	<i>Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig</i>
<i>PMB</i>	<i>Project Management Board</i>
<i>PMP</i>	<i>Project Management Plan</i>
<i>STAB</i>	<i>Scientific and Technical Advisory Board</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

7. Introduction to Möbius

7.1. Project summary

Möbius is an initiative funded under the European Commission's Horizon 2020 programme which has aimed to modernise the **European book publishing industry** by remodelling traditional value chains and business models, uncovering the prosumer's potential, and delivering new enriched media experiences. Its main challenge has been to renovate publishing into an economic and cultural agent, by embracing digital transformation.

This renovation has been achieved via an **innovative approach** to prosumer intelligence which has allowed for the creation of the prosumer's intelligence toolkit. Digital methods from **computational social science** in cooperation with relevant end-users have been developed to analyse the fandom community. Subsequently, the data has been explored thanks to interactive data visualisation and a user-friendly dashboard.

Finally, the **Möbius Book**, which is an immersive, interactive and cross-media book experience, has been created with the help of two experimental productions: *The Influence of Blue* by Giulio Ravizza and *Fantasy into Möbius*, by Filippo Rubulotta the winner of the Call for manuscripts.

The Möbius project is composed of 11 partners hailing from different sectors, such as the publishing industry, technologists, social scientists, social innovators, and artists.

7.2. Deliverable overview

The Möbius's Dissemination and Communication Plan, as defined in Task 6.1 (Dissemination and Communication) of Work Package 6 (Maximizing impact) is led by FMWC (Leader of Task 6.1 and 6.3). Whereas MVB leads the Exploitation Roadmaps task (T6.2). Hence, the principal goal of this deliverable is to report all the dissemination and communication activities and exploitation and IPR management roadmaps for each output of the project.

This deliverable presents a straightforward and explicit report of the project's communication and dissemination results, information and messages communicated, tools and channels used, and events organised and attended. As also, the routes for exploitation and the different IP claims provided by partners will be exposed.

All partners in Möbius have been involved in dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities, by supplying content, developing scientific publications, participating in events, promoting the project's outcomes and putting their efforts on maximizing the project's impact.

8. Impact Maximisation Plan

FMWC leads the dissemination and communication activities, which include dissemination, awareness, and advocacy work in the technologically driven side of the media ecosystem.

The specific tasks developed during the project as part of the impact maximization plan are as follows:

- Promote and position Möbius in relevant industrial, scientific and policy fora through dissemination activities, encouraging re-use and verification of development and results following the principles: open science, open innovation and open to the world.
- Ensure broad visibility and raise awareness about Möbius, spreading knowledge about the project and its results offline and online.
- Reach, stimulate and engage users and stakeholders in Möbius piloting activities, including the open call for manuscripts.

Figure 1: Phases of the Möbius communication strategy

Möbius's communication and dissemination plan has been executed throughout a series of three phases, each strategically planned right from the project's inception and fully explained in D6.1. These phases are evidence of FMWC and the Möbius consortium's proactive approach and dedication to achieving the communication objectives. This report will dive deeper into the plan that has been executed, highlighting the milestones, strategies, and outcomes in detail.

The Möbius project's communication and dissemination strategy was significantly influenced by the evolution of both technology and the publishing sector throughout the project's lifetime, generating different challenges and opportunities.

On the one hand, the project's cross-sectoral approach has presented a valuable opportunity to foster synergies with various other initiatives and enhance Möbius's overall visibility. However, when it comes to aspects of communication and dissemination, it has, at times, introduced a certain degree of complexity in effectively involving a diverse range of stakeholders. The sheer diversity of interests and the rapid pace of innovations in the market, such as the emergence of 5G, artificial intelligence, and virtual reality, have made it difficult to maintain a clear differentiation in the market.

In this way, the *prosumer* concept has been challenging to explain, as throughout the project it has been perceived that people scarcely identify themselves as prosumers. For this reason, FMWC had to reach this audience through readers and authors. Despite this, an important amount of this target audience was found and successfully engaged within Möbius's activities.

On the other hand, the project also identified other relevant stakeholders, ensuring that its outreach efforts were well-targeted (see them listed in the following chapter). This comprehensive understanding of Möbius' audiences resulted in the creation of effective targeted messaging. Additionally, the project had a robust visual identity, which played a vital role in promoting the brand and conveying its value proposition. This visual consistency helped create a recognisable presence in the market.

Furthermore, Möbius successfully participated in a wide range of events and activities within the publishing sector. These engagements resulted in establishing a presence, building relationships, and showcasing the project's relevance within the industry. Leveraging these strengths while addressing the weaknesses will be essential in shaping a more refined and adaptable communication and dissemination strategy for future projects.

9. Target Stakeholders for Möbius's Maximization Plan

Möbius's target stakeholders are grouped into seven categories, as stated in D6.1. They are listed to build, promote, and develop a sustainable network:

- Prosumer Sector
- Policy and Society
- Publishing Sector
- Media Industry
- ICT Sector
- Research
- Academia, and Open-Source Communities
- General Public

Figure 2: Map of the stakeholders

10. Communication and Dissemination Activities

The communication and dissemination strategy has been executed to reach the project's objectives, with a primary focus **on enhancing the visibility of Möbius**. This extends even beyond the project's duration, aiming to foster the adoption and acceptance of Möbius' value proposition within the Next Generation Media ecosystem and society.

Möbius has engaged in **diverse channels** to accomplish these specific goals and developed plans to participate in forums to engage society at large. The communication materials created to give visibility to the project include standard tools such as visual identity, website, video creation, blog articles, promotional materials, newsletters, press releases, and social media engagement. These have helped to connect with key stakeholders in publishing, prosumer communities, the technology sector, policy and society, and the media ecosystem, as stated in D6.1.

The following table outlines a list of communication activities with Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that have helped to assess and maximise the project's impact. These activities have aimed **to raise awareness, generate interest, and foster public acceptance of the transformation taking place in the book industry**. To effectively engage with key stakeholders and showcase Möbius Book Applications, the Prosumers Intelligence Toolkit, and

the Möbius Book Experiences, FMWC has implemented communication and dissemination plans that build upon the tools and channels mentioned in D6.1.

Item	Communication activities	KPIs
Website	The website holds general information about the project, blog articles, events, newsletter subscription, and open call information.	(M1-M36) 15.000 visitors 3000 clicks
Brand Identity	Design of the logo and branding guidelines, including identification of the most relevant colours and most readable font codes. Creation of templates for presentations in different formats. The visual identity is applied to all communication materials.	(M3) Logo, Brand, Template
Videos	Creation of six videos: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 for communicating the general message of the project • 1 initial and 1 final with the results: one accounting for user-driven activities, paying particular attention to the direct voices of the target participants involved • 1 “making of” for each of the two experimental productions • 1 accounting for the policy and business messages 	(M1-M36) 6 100 online view per video
Blog articles	Blog articles will be published to address different stakeholders about: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project activities and progress • Technological developments • The publishing industry • Immersive experiences • Other topics of interest 	(M1-M36) 24
Promotional material	Flyers and brochures presenting key information about the project, and event banners for the social media accounts	(M1-M36) > 50
Newsletters	Elaboration of a trimestral newsletter that communicates project highlights and announcements to the stakeholder community	(M1-M36) 12 250 persons reached.
Press releases (PR)	Distribution among media of paid and free articles, across both sectorial online and traditional magazines, including short news or promotional spaces (visual)	(M1-M36) 10 PR 10 publications

and Media coverage		50 Editorial & clippings
Social Media	Twitter and LinkedIn are used to communicate with the followers. Instagram, given its prevalence among the younger generation and the publishing sector, will also serve as communication channel.	(M1-M36) 3000 followers 3000 posts
Marketing material	Tote bags, stickers, notebooks, and pencils with project branding for use at different events, and for user engagement activities.	(M1-M36) 2

Table 1: List of the Möbius communication activities

10.1 Tools and Channels

The following section will present the communication tools and channels used throughout the project's lifetime. It will develop the indicators to quantitatively and qualitatively fulfill the impact of the communication and dissemination plan mentioned and expected in the previous section.

10.1.1 Website

The Möbius website has been the central entry point for all public material, including public results and deliverables, downloadable applications, and informational material. In this way, the website features a blog section, links to relevant websites, and event details. It was launched in March 2021, and since then, has been restructured with the sections below, meaning a change in the website metrics analysed, as explained in the following section.

The website has a legal warning (Cookies) and a policy that promises the fulfilment of the GDPR.

Figure 3: Möbius website (homepage)

The website is structured into **9 sections**. The different pages are described as follows:

1. **Homepage:** The homepage of the Möbius project website serves as an introduction to the project. It features a project logo, a banner with a button highlighting several news and innovations at different times of the project, and a brief mission statement or project summary. Visitors may find links to key sections of the website. While scrolling down, there's a dedicated multimedia area with videos, social media, and a calendar with the upcoming events where piloting will take place. When someone is a first-time visitor to the Möbius website, a pop-up appears with an explanation of the cookies used and gives the option to allow or deny what is preferred.
2. **Our Story:** This page details the description of the project and its objectives. It is accompanied by a video. It also includes information about the consortium members. Visual elements such as an infographic of the project partners have been added.
3. **Closed Open Call:** Since the open call was opened on November 8th, 2021, and closed on January 15th, 2022, the webpage has evolved, acquiring several formats

according to the users' participation needs. At that moment, there was an “Apply now” button plus an explanation on how to participate and the terms and conditions. Now, a disclaimer mentions that it is closed, and a button redirects to the Winners' web pages described below. Visitors can also find the video of the Möbius Awards Ceremony and the description of the open call process.

4. **Winners:** This page presents the winning manuscripts and the authors of the Möbius Open Call for Manuscripts. Each of the stories is available to read, as well as watchable via video interviews with the three winners.
5. **Möbius Book Experience:** This page explains the goals behind the Möbius Book Experiences and offers a description of all of them, including the pictures created by the author, a button linked to the creation process, and the adapted Möbius Book. It also includes the downloadable file version of the VR headsets.
6. **Möbius Innovative Applications:** This page briefly describes the Möbius Innovative Applications, being the Möbius Book (Player and Creator) and the Prosumers Intelligence Toolkit. It is also dedicated to explaining the testing procedure in real life with users at several events to improve their go-to-market opportunities. Each of the applications is linked to its own website. There is also a calendar of the different events where these activities will take place.
7. **News:** This section features the latest news, press releases, events, public deliverables, interviews, articles, and newsletters related to the Möbius project. Visitors can stay informed about project milestones and recent developments.
8. **Community:** This page contains specific information about the network of ecosystem-related projects to forge synergies. The ICT-44 Next Generation Media projects (Möbius sibling projects) are included. Also, supportive partners such as MediaFutures or Aldus Up are included. Each of these projects is adequately described and linked to its own website.
9. **Contact us:** This section contains a contact form to interact with the Möbius project when users have doubts, suggestions, or questions.

Audience Metrics (Google Analytics, March 2021 –January 2024)

Users & Views

Users	10k
Views	43k
Average time	1m 13s

Language, country, city

Users by Country

COUNTRY	USERS
Ireland	1.4K
Spain	1.2K
Germany	841
Italy	668
United States	620
Netherlands	420
Belgium	403

[View countries](#) →

Users by Town/City

TOWN/CITY	USERS
Dublin	1.4K
Barcelona	435
Helsinki	283
Amsterdam	248
Madrid	205
Milan	168
Paris	168

Users by Language

Figure 4: Google Analytics infographics on Language, Country and City

Top content

Top web pages		Views
1	Home	17867
2	The power of prosumers in publishing	1124
3	Our story	290
4	News	347
5	Möbius Book Experience	263

Top materials		Views
1	The Möbius interactive book experience arrives in the Fantastic Adventure Night of the Leipzig Book Fair 2023	111
2	The Möbius project participates in a round table about the role of data in transforming the publishing sector in the Mobile World Congress 2023	108
3	Innovations in the publishing sector	80
4	Möbius celebrates its Closing Event at Frankfurt Book Fair 2023	78
5	How data is transforming the publishing sector: Möbius Project at MWC23	67

This data reveals a strong preference for English as the primary language among Möbius webpage users since the website is predominantly written in English. Moreover, regarding the geographic distribution of the users, the majority are located within European countries and cities, with a particular emphasis on regions where the Möbius partners are based. In terms of webpage engagement, it's evident that the "Home" page is the most frequented, serving as the initial landing point for visitors. Additionally, materials dedicated to the project's events have emerged as the most successful and engaging content for Möbius's web users.

10.1.2. Videos

During the project's lifetime, several videos have been created to explain the project idea and outputs, report on attended events, and broadcast recorded online events. The videos have been uploaded online, attached to the respective blog post or website section, promoted on social media, and showcased across different project presentations and events.

In D6.1, six videos were planned, resulting in the following outputs:

- **Two videos explaining the general message of the project:**
 - [Möbius Book Experience](#)
 - [The power of prosumers in publishing](#)
- **Two videos showing user-driven activities:** Summary videos of our attendance at events: [London](#), [Amsterdam](#), [Readmagine Madrid](#), [Book Pride Milano](#), [interviews with the winners](#) and [Giulio Ravizza](#), [Interviews with the partners](#).
- **Videos of the two experimental productions:**
 - [Leipzig](#)
 - [Frankfurt](#)

In addition, more videos were created to fulfil social media needs, given that static content is no longer engaging to online audiences. Thus, more videos had to be recorded and edited to increase Möbius' social media impressions and engagement. **Six of the videos managed to reach more than 100 views, one of them more than 200.** FMWC values this as great, given that the KPI for videos has successfully been accomplished. The videos with the top number of views are:

1. [Möbius: The power of prosumers in publishing](#) (214 views)
2. [The Möbius Book Experience](#) (113 views)
3. [The Möbius Book Experience \(Subtitles\)](#) (208 views)
4. [Fantastic Adventure Night, Leipzig](#) (131 views)
5. [The Möbius Awards Ceremony](#) (125 views)
6. [Möbius interview with Iris Jennes at the Leipzig Book Fair](#) (108 views)

The top viewed videos listed above have been key in promoting and explaining the Möbius project. The first four, focusing on the project's core concepts, have been very valuable resources at events and presentations, with effective social media campaigns boosting their viewership. The Möbius Awards Ceremony, marked by high attendance and post-event sharing by Open Call winners, had a powerful impact. Furthermore, the video "*Fantastic Adventure Night, Leipzig*" has contributed to project visibility. These videos have raised awareness and interest in the Möbius project through events and extensive online promotion.

	Title	Date	Views	Link
1	Möbius Web Promotional Video	16/06/2021	27	video
2	Möbius The power of prosumers in publishing	23/06/2021	214	video
3	The Möbius Open Call is officially launched!	24/11/2021	9	video
4	The Möbius Book Experience	20/01/2022	113	video

5	Möbius Awards Ceremony Meet the winners of the Open Call for Manuscripts	27/04/2022	125	video
6	Interview to the 2nd Möbius Open Call Winner: Rodrigo Do Ó	14/06/2022	23	video
7	Interview to the 3rd Möbius Open Call Winner: Ciro Neri	14/06/2022	59	video
8	Interview to the first Möbius Open Call winner: Filippo Rubulotta	08/07/2022	49	video
9	Meet our partners: interview to Patricia Castillo, Eurecat	05/08/2022	29	video
10	Meet our partners: Enrico Turrin (FEP)	05/08/2022	18	video
11	Meet our partners: Spela Zalokar (EnoLL)	05/08/2022	56	video
12	Meet our partners: Iris Jennes (IMEC)	05/08/2022	29	video
13	Meet our partners: George Ioannidis (IN2)	05/08/2022	17	video
14	Meet our partners: Markus Loeffler (KKW)	05/08/2022	6	video
15	Meet our partners: Emircan Karabuğa (KU Leuven)	05/08/2022	3	video
16	Meet our partners: Simona de Rosa (DEN Institute)	05/08/2022	20	video
17	Möbius at Ars Electronica 2022	14/11/2022	13	video
18	Möbius 4th Plenary meeting Brussels	23/11/2022	19	video
19	Möbius Policy Workshop: "Book publishing in the age of platforms"	30/11/2022	57	video
20	The role of data in transforming the publishing and the media sectors	08/03/2023	47	video
21	Möbius at the Book Pride 2023 in Milan	13/03/2023	60	video
22	Möbius at the Mobile World Congress 2023	16/03/2023	13	video
23	Interview to Simona De Rosa after the Möbius panel at Mobile World Congress 2023	16/03/2023	38	video
24	Come to visit Möbius at the London Book Fair 2023!	19/04/2023	34	video
25	Interview with Spela Zalokar from ENoLL at the London Book Fair 2023	04/05/2023	29	video

26	Möbius interactive book at the Fantastic Adventure Night of the Leipzig Book Fair 2023	02/06/2023	131	video
27	Möbius Interview with the writer Giulio Ravizza - Leipzig Book Fair 2023	02/06/2023	47	video
28	Möbius Interview with Iris Jennes, Researcher at IMEC - Leipzig Book Fair 2023	02/06/2023	110	video
29	Möbius Interview with Markus Loeffler, Founder of Kunstkraftwerk venue - Leipzig Book Fair 2023	02/06/2023	42	video
30	Möbius Interview with Rosa Maria Araujo, Möbius Coordinator - Leipzig Book Fair 2023	02/06/2023	69	video
31	Möbius Closing Event at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 Interview to Markus Löffler, KKW	30/11/2023	1	video
32	Möbius Closing Event at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 Interview to Anabel Acuña, MVB	30/11/2023	10	video
33	Möbius Closing Event at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 Interview to Alexandru Stan, IN2	30/11/2023	15	video
34	Möbius Closing Event at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 Interview to Miha Kovac, University Ljubljana	30/11/2023	12	video
35	Möbius at the IBC Amsterdam 2023 Next Generation Media Projects	30/11/2023	2	video
36	Möbius Prosumers Intelligence Toolkit Workshop at Readmagine Madrid 2023	30/11/2023	2	video
37	It's a wrap! Möbius Closing Event at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023	01/12/2023	66	video

10.1.3 Blog articles

A series of blog articles have been produced to address different stakeholders regarding project activities and progress, technological developments of the project, the publishing industry and immersive experiences, and other topics of interest. These articles have aimed to present the project activities and their progress, as well as the technological developments, as much as the immersive experiences. Interviews from the different partners have been set up to present the participation of each of them to the public. The consortium has also prepared general content about publishing to provide context, relevant information, and data about the publishing sector.

The content has been divided into different categories, such as news, articles, press releases, public deliverables, interviews, newsletters, and events. 87 posts have been created in total.

	Title	Type	Target group	Date	Twitter	Linkedin	Web
1	MÖBIUS: the digital awakening of the European publishing sector	News	General public	27/04/2021			link
2	The publishing sector, at the edge of a fundamental change	Article	General public	17/05/2021	link		link
3	The end of books, a non-sense	Article	General public	21/06/2021	link		link
4	The business of book publishing: when the encyclopedia salesperson is uploaded to the cloud	Article	General public	09/09/2021	link		link
5	Are you a fan fiction enthusiast?	News	Authors	14/09/2021	link		link
6	Möbius call for manuscripts offers fantasy authors the chance to publish their first cross-media literary work	Press Release	Authors	08/11/2021	link		link
7	Book publishing and the European Green Deal: Social dreaming for cultural actors	News	General public	22/11/2021	link		link

8	Meet our partners: Eurecat	Interview	General public	22/11/2021	link		link
9	The Möbius Consortium celebrated its first face-to-face meeting	News	General public	07/12/2021	link		link
10	#1 Newsletter – The Möbius website has officially launched	Newsletter	General public	13/12/2021			link
11	Meet our partners: Mobile World Capital Barcelona	Interview	General public	15/12/2021	link		link
12	#2 Newsletter – Möbius Open Call is officially launched	Newsletter	General public	16/12/2021			link
13	Meet our partners: Design Entrepreneurship Institute	Interview	General public	01/02/2022	link		link
14	The Möbius Team shares data on the Open Call for Manuscripts	News	Authors and Readers	18/02/2022	link		link
15	The publishing industry through a cross-media approach. The example of the Möbius project in exploring new applications for the book sector and the role of the prosumer	Article	Technological sector	08/03/2022	link		link

16	#3 Newsletter – Discover the data on our recently closed Möbius Open Call for manuscripts!	Newsletter	General public	09/03/2022			link
17	The Möbius Project at the Mobile World Congress 2022!	Event	General public	09/03/2022	link		link
18	Predicting content popularity in fanfiction communities	News	Technological sector, publishers	13/04/2022	link		link
19	Meet our partners: MVB	Interview	General public	13/04/2022	link		link
20	Reading Rationals: Consciously Unconscious Customer Centricity	Article	Publishers	21/04/2022			link
21	Business exploitation scenarios for prosumer book publishing	Article	Publishers	26/04/2022	link		link
22	#4 Newsletter – Möbius Awards Ceremony	Newsletter	General public	06/05/2022			link
23	The winners of the Open Call for Manuscripts were announced at the Möbius Awards Ceremony	Press Release	General public	10/05/2022	link	link	link
24	#5 Newsletter – Meet the winners of the Möbius	Newsletter	General public	24/05/2022			link

	Open Call for manuscripts!						
25	Meet our partners: IN2	Interview	General public	01/06/2022			link
26	Möbius at Future Week 2022	Event	General public	08/06/2022			link
27	Meet our partners: IMEC	Interview	General public	21/06/2022			link
28	Innovations in the publishing sector	Article	Publishers	12/07/2022	link	link	link
29	Meet our partners: FEP	Interview	General public	02/08/2022	link	link	link
30	Meet our partners: EnoLL	Interview	General public	02/08/2022	link	link	link
31	Möbius at the Frankfurt Buchmesse: “Creative and Culture Industries: transform and innovate to enable new business opportunities”	Event	General public	29/09/2022	link	link	link
32	Immersion or Disruption? Möbius Pilot 1 Results on Readers’ Evaluation of and Requirements for 3D-audio as a Tool to Support Immersion in Digital Reading Practices	Article	Technological sector, publishers	30/09/2022			link

33	#6 Newsletter – Möbius at the Frankfurt Buchmesse: “Creative and Culture Industries: transform and innovate to enable new business opportunities”	Newsletter	General public	05/10/2022			link
34	Möbius has participated in the Frankfurter Buchmesse 2022	Press Release	General public	02/11/2022	link	link	link
35	Möbius at Ars Electronica 2022	Event	General public	14/11/2022	link	link	link
36	Möbius fourth plenary meeting in Brussels	News	General public	23/11/2022	link	link	link
37	#7 Newsletter – Möbius is organising a policy workshop on “Book publishing in the age of platforms”	Newsletter	General public	30/11/2022	link	link	link
38	The European Project Möbius organised a policy workshop on ‘Book publishing in the age of platforms’	Press Release	Publishers, policy-makers	01/12/2022	link	link	link
39	D6.1 Initial Strategic dissemination, communication and public engagement plans	Deliverable	General public	19/12/2022			link

40	D4.4 Möbius Production Script	Deliverable	General public	19/12/2022			link
41	D4.2 Möbius open call: Fantasy	Deliverable	General public	19/12/2022			link
42	D3.2 Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit minimum viable product	Deliverable	General public	19/12/2022			link
43	D2.1 Möbius theoretical framework: opportunities, benefits, and risks	Deliverable	General public	19/12/2022			link
44	D1.4 Initial Data Management Plan	Deliverable	General public	19/12/2022			link
45	D1.3 Ethical requirements for human participation in research	Deliverable	General public	19/12/2022			link
46	D1.2 Protection of Personal Data (POPD)	Deliverable	General public	19/12/2022			link
47	Meet our partners: Bookabook	Interview	General public	19/12/2022	link	link	link
48	Give your creation copyright protection with the Möbius solution	Article	Publishers, authors	13/02/2023	link	link	link
49	The Möbius project participates in a round table about the role of data in transforming the publishing sector in the	Event	General public	13/02/2023	link	link	link

	Mobile World Congress 2023						
50	Möbius' Pilot Phases summary: Engaging users in the development of the project's products	Article	Readers, authors, publishers	20/02/2023	link	link	link
51	Möbius project showcases its contributions to innovate in the publishing sector at Book Pride Milano 2023	Event	Readers, authors, publishers	28/02/2023	link	link	link
52	How data is transforming the publishing sector: Möbius Project at MWC23	Event	Technological sector, publishers	01/03/2023	link	link	link
53	Engaging users in the development of Möbius: How did users evaluate the Möbius Creator in pilot phase 2?	Article	Readers, authors, publishers	02/03/2023			link
54	Engaging users in the development of Möbius: How did readers evaluate the Möbius Player in pilot phase 2?	Article	Readers, authors, publishers	02/03/2023			link
56	Engaging users in the development of Möbius:	Article	Readers, authors, publishers	02/03/2023			link

	How did users evaluate the Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit in pilot phase 2?						
57	Crowd publishing	Article	Publishers	06/03/2023	link	link	link
58	The Möbius interactive book experience arrives in the Fantastic Adventure Night of the Leipzig Book Fair 2023	Event	General public	21/03/2023	link	link	link
59	The Möbius Project showcases and tests the Innovative Applications at The London Book Fair 2023	Event	General public	26/04/2023	link	link	link
60	The Möbius Mobile Immersive Book Box landed at the Fantastic Adventure Night of the Leipzig Book Fair 2023	Event	General Public	03/05/2023	link	link	link
61	Möbius attends Salone Internazionale del Libro di Torino 2023 to test the Innovative Applications	Event	General Public	24/05/2023	link	link	link
62	Möbius presented the Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit in an interactive	Event	Readers, authors, publishers	12/06/2023	link	link	link

	workshop at Readmagine 2023						
63	Möbius explained how 3D audio can improve digital reading at ACM IMX 2023	Event	Technological sector	18/06/2023	link	link	link
64	Möbius speaks about immersive reading at the MediaFutures Demo Days 2023	Event	General public	23/06/2023	link	link	link
65	Möbius celebrates its Closing Event at Frankfurt Book Fair 2023	Press Release	General public	24/08/2023	link	link	link
66	The Next Generation Media projects join forces to showcase European innovation in the sector	Event	General public	20/09/2023	link	link	link
67	Introducing Möbius' Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit: a dashboard to gather essential knowledge on readers' habits	Article	Publishers	28/09/2023	link	link	link
68	Immersive reading is the new trend in publishing	Article	Publishers	28/09/2023	link	link	link
69	Testing Innovation: Möbius at	Event	General Public	04/10/2023	link	link	link

	OpenLivingLab Days 2023						
70	Möbius offers an immersive reading experience at Bright Festival Connect 2023	Event	General Public	05/10/2023	link	link	link
71	Möbius at Madrid Book Fair 2023	Event	General Public	23/10/2023	link	link	link
72	Möbius Celebrates Its Closing Event at Frankfurt Book Fair 2023	Event	General Public	23/10/2023	link	link	link
73	#11 Newsletter – October Digest: The Möbius Immersive Storytelling Adventures	Newsletter	General Public	09/11/2023			link
74	Möbius at Buch Wien 2023	Press Release	General Public	21/11/2023	link	link	link
75	Frankfurt Flashback: It's a Wrap!	Event	General Public	30/11/2023	link	link	link
76	Möbius Leaves Its Mark at the Ljubljana Book Fair 2023	Event	General Public	04/12/2023	link	link	link
77	Meet our partners: Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig	Interview	General Public	05/12/2023	link	link	link
78	Unveiling the Copyright Implications of Online Creation and Sharing of Literary Content in the EU	Article	Publishers	20/12/2023	link	link	link

79	Meet our partner: KU Leuven Centre for IT and IP Law (CiTiP)	Interview	General Public	28/12/2023	link	link	link
80	Möbius experiences: Immersive art installations and Mobile Book Box	Article	General Public	05/01/2024	link	link	link
81	D2.2 – Möbius Technology Blueprint	Deliverable	General public	15/01/2024			link
82	D3.4 – Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	Deliverable	General public	16/01/2024			link
83	D3.5 – Final Report on Prosumer Business Models, cross-sector scalability and IP Framework	Deliverable	General public	16/01/2024			link
84	D4.5 – Möbius Book Final Prototype	Deliverable	General public	16/01/2024			link
85	D5.2 – Möbius experiences	Deliverable	General public	16/01/2024			link
86	D3.1 – Knowledge extraction models	Deliverable	General public	16/01/2024			link
87	D5.1 – Möbius books productions report	Deliverable	General public	16/01/2024			link

Table 2: List of blog posts

10.1.4 Flyers and Marketing material

Flyers and brochures have been created, including essential information on the project, to be printed for use at events. In addition, images have been created for the social media accounts and adapted to said events that the project has participated in. Finally, tote bags, roll-ups, stickers, and notebooks have been created following Möbius' project branding for these different events and user engagement activities.

Figure 5: Marketing Materials at events

This marketing material has been instrumental during Möbius' attendance at events. Flyers have visually illustrated the project for the target audience, making it easier for the Möbius partners to explain Möbius and our activities, especially during Pilot Phase 3a and b. Many visitors were very interested in the tote bags and notebooks, and for this reason the consortium used them as a marketing strategy, giving them as a prize after testing one of the Möbius applications.

Figure 6: Marketing Material at the London Book Fair 2023

10.1.5 Press releases

Press notes were distributed among media and press contacts. These included paid and free articles in sectorial online and traditional magazines, short pieces of news, or promotional spaces.

A total of **12 Press releases** have been distributed during the project. Some of these were to communicate essential milestones of the project, such as the kick-off or the open call. However, FMWC noticed that the press releases that helped the project obtain more impact were related to the attended events or to the activities the consortium organised. Thus, the project's developments were introduced within the press releases related to each milestone depending on the event attended.

The following table showcases the press releases sent through the platform Meltwater, which offers social listening and social analytics, solutions across media, social, consumer and sales

intelligence. Within Möbius, this software was previously used to share press releases and analyse their impact.

Partner	Title	Emails sent	Open rate
FMWC	Möbius: The digital awakening of the European Publishing sector	145	28,97%
FMWC	Möbius Call for Manuscripts offers fantasy authors the chance to publish their first cross-media literary work	442	21,04%
FMWC	Möbius: The winners of the Open Call for Manuscripts were announced at the Möbius Awards Ceremony	565	35,35%
FMWC	Möbius Policy Workshop on "Book publishing in the age of platforms"	479	34,51%
FMWC	Möbius at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2022	409	33,39%

Table 3: List of press release using Meltwater

Having tested out Meltwater for the beginning of the project, it was detected that it was not reaching the expected impact. For this reason, another platform was contracted, which resulted in much better results. The following table showcases the press releases sent through the platform EinPressWire, a service for professional communicators and organisations that need to get their news in front of the media, stakeholders, and the public. EIN Presswire owns and maintains its own proprietary distribution technologies.

Partner	Title	Clippings
FMWC	The Möbius interactive book experience arrives in the Fantastic Adventure Night of the Leipzig Book Fair 2023	209
FMWC	The Next Generation Media projects join forces to showcase European innovation in the sector	125
FMWC	Möbius Celebrates Its Closing Event at Frankfurt Book Fair 2023	214
FMWC	The new Möbius Book fosters reading with prosumer-driven immersive multimedia experiences	232
FMWC	To be sent (about the Closing Event at MWC24)	N/A

Table 4: List of press release Ein PressWire

Not only FMWC sent press releases, but also two were sent by the partner Eurecat:

Partner	Title
EUT	How data is transforming the publishing sector: Möbius Project at MWC23
EUT	Eurecat assaja una experiència immersiva de la lectura en format digital amb efectes especials en audio 3D i creacions musicals

Table 5: List of press releases sent by Eurecat

Thanks to these platforms and its media contacts, as well as each partner’s communication department, the Möbius project **has obtained 697 clippings**, having reached media outlets such as AP News, El Periódico, La Vanguardia or Catalunya Ràdio. The project also appeared in important institutions and organisations such as Generalitat de Catalunya, HADEA EC, Ametic and Escritores.org.

Figure 7: Highlighted outlets where Möbius was published

Möbius has also published six articles in outlets specialised in publishing and law. It could not arrive to publish ten to different media, instead it reached more than **600 clippings**. It also reached 4 scientific journals and published 87 blog posts on the website.

Partner	Title	Media	Link
FEP / FMWC	Individuality Underpins BookTok’s Profound Impact on Book Sales	State of Digital Publishing	Link
KU Leuven	Insights from the Möbius Project: Unveiling the Copyright Implications of Online Creation and Sharing of Literary Content in the EU	KU Leuven Website	Link
EUT	La digitalización al servicio de la literatura	Inedit	Link
DEN	Blurring Boundaries	TOYS Magazine	Link
MVB	Auf den Spuren der kreativen Prosumer	Börsenblatt	Link
FMWC	The latest tech innovations in the book industry: The Möbius culmination in 4YFN	4YFN	Link

Table 5: Publications in websites and digital newspapers

10.1.6 Events

Möbius has participated in major events within the publishing industry (Frankfurt Book Fair, Leipzig Book Fair), as well as more technological and media industry-oriented events such as the Mobile World Congress Barcelona and ISE. During the period March 2021 – February 2024, **Möbius organised and participated in a total of 70 events**. Below are the details of each event Möbius attended and organised:

- **Mobile World Congress Barcelona:** Möbius Project participated in three editions of the Mobile World Congress Barcelona, engaging with mobile operators, tech providers, policy influencers, media leaders, academia, and the general public. The event yielded valuable insights, expanded the project’s network, and paved the way for future initiatives to shape the future of technology. The last Mobile World Congress attended by the project was an organised activity for the Möbius Closing Event (details in D6.3).
- **Technological and media events:** Möbius has participated in 9 technological and media-related events, given that it is a cross-sectoral and multi-disciplinary project.

These include events such as: All about Audio, Future Week, Integrates Systems Europe (ISE), NEM SB, Ars Electronica and International Broadcasting Convention (IBC).

- **Frankfurt Book Fair:** The Frankfurt Book Fair is the most important international trade fair for publishing and content. Experts from global publishing meet partners from the technology industry and related creative industries, such as film and games. Möbius has participated in three Buchmessen events, the last of them being part of the Möbius Closing Event (details in D6.3). Möbius was presented to publishers, prosumers, the creative and cultural industries, policy and society, and academia, researchers and open-source communities.
- **Book fairs around Europe:** Möbius has also participated in 10 book fairs all around Europe, not only to communicate and disseminate the project, but also to reach readers, authors and publishers aiming to test Möbius' Applications and showcase the Möbius Book Experiences. Some of these events attended include: Book Pride, The London Book Fair, the Leipzig Book Fair, Salone del Libro di Torino, Readmagine, Liber Madrid, the Vienna Book Fair and the Ljubljana Book Fair.
- **FEP Meetings:** These meetings were organised by the Federation of European Publishers (FEP). They update various National Publishers Associations (such as BOEV, Germany), about the book sector at European level, and plan FEP's activities for the upcoming months. One section of these meetings is always dedicated to all the European projects that the FEP works with, such as Möbius. These sessions were regularly used to spread awareness about the project and recruit relevant stakeholders from the publishing sector. Some of these sessions focused exclusively on Möbius, such as the November 2023 meeting, which was dedicated to showcasing the latest version of the Prosumers Intelligence Toolkit to the audience and to gather their feedback on this version of the application. The presentations contributed in general to the knowledge and awareness of Möbius and its outputs across the book publishing community, provided specific insights into the Prosumer Intelligence Kit, also through a live demonstration, and allowed for the recruitment of participants for different project activities.
- **Networking events:** Möbius has participated in four networking events to meet with other European projects or publishing sector ecosystems, and network with similar initiatives with whom it could cross-collaborate, such as CDTI Valencia, Media Futures Final Event, Festival 42 or Creative Shift Creative Innovazione Council. Participating in this kind of event has broadened Möbius' impact and reach. These engagements provided opportunities to establish meaningful connections within other European projects and publishing sector ecosystems, fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange with like-minded initiatives. Through these interactions, Möbius gained access to diverse perspectives and expertise and paved the way for cross-collaborations, enhancing the project's capacity to innovate and drive positive change in the media and creative industries.

- Conferences:** IMEC, one of the consortium partners, also attended two conferences. From 10 to 11 February 2022, IMEC was present at the "Eetmaal van de Communicatiewetenschap". This Eetmaal edition took place online and centred on the theme 'Diversity, democracy & communication'. Here, IMEC presented the requirements for digital innovation in the European publishing industry. IMEC was also present at the ACM International Conference on Interactive Media Experiences (IMX) in Nantes, which took place from 12-15 June 2023. The theme of the conference was Imaginary in Motion. There, the paper "Immersion or Disruption? Readers' Evaluation of and Requirements for (3D) Audio as a Tool to Support Immersion in Digital Reading Practice" written by Imec, was presented. These conferences were used to introduce the works within the Möbius project and gain information about similar projects through presentations and networking at the conference.
- Own Organised Events:** Möbius has also organised its events online, such as the Möbius Awards Ceremony, the policy-making workshop, and the online workshops to test the Möbius applications. However, it co-organised activities in physical events such as the S+T+Arts Day or the meeting with the sibling projects in Future Week Bergen. It also organised the Fantastic Adventure Night in Leipzig and several activities within the Möbius Closing Event in the frame of the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 and the Mobile World Congress 2024. Möbius also participated in the Open Living Labs Day, an event organised by ENoLL, one of the Möbius partners, to test and showcase the applications and the experiences.

No	Start Date	End Date	Event	Target	Organised/ Attended	Type of participation	Where	Attendees	Partner
1	20/05/2021	20/05/2021	All about audio	ICT Sector	Attended	Scouting	Online	-	FMWC
2	10/06/2021	10/06/2021	FEP Meetings	Publishing Industry	Organised	Recruitment of people, platform, script	Online	43	FEP
3	01/06/2021	02/06/2021	ISE 2021	ICT sector	Attended	Booth	Barcelona	16.000	EUT
4	28/06/2021	1/7/2021	Mobile World Congress	ICT Sector	Attended	Booth	Barcelona	35.000	FMWC
5	9/9/2021	9/9/2021	FEP Meetings	Publishing Industry	Organised	Recruitment of people, platform	Online	45	FEP

						m, script			
6	20/10/2021	24/10/2021	Frankfurt Book Fair	Publishers and publisher associations	Attended	Panel	Frankfurt/Online	73.000	IN2, DEN, FMWC, FEP, MVB
7	10/11/2021	10/11/2021	FEP Meetings	Publishers and publisher associations	Organised	Recruitment of people, platform, script	Brussels	40	FEP
8	3/11/2021	7/11/2021	Festival 42: Primer festival de gèneres fantàstics de Barcelona	General Public	Attended	Marketing materials	Barcelona	6.000	FMWC
9	11/24/2021	11/24/2021	Creative Shift Creative innovation Council	Policy & Society	Attended	Networking / Dissemination meeting	Milan	30	DEN
10	10/02/2022	11/02/2022	Etmaal van de communicatiewetenschap	Research	Organised	Recruitment of people, platform, script, presentation	Brussels (online)	374	IMEC
11	14/02/2022	14/02/2022	FEP Meetings	Publishing Industry	Organised	Recruitment of people, platform, script,	Online	43	FEP
12	28/02/2022	03/03/2022	Mobile World Congress	ICT Sector	Organised	Booth	Barcelona	60.000	FMWC
13	11/3/2022	11/3/2022	FEP Meetings - GA	Publishing Industry	Organised	Information	Brussels	33	FEP
14	6/04/2022	6/04/2022	CDTI Valencia	Research	Attended	Recruitment of people, platform	Valencia	300	FMWC

						m, script			
15	25/04/2022	21/04/2022	Möbius Awards Ceremony	All stakeholders	Organised	Recruitment of people, platform, script, panel	Online	64	EUT, BookaBook, FMWC
16	4/3/2022	6/3/2022	BookPride 2022: Fiera nazionale dell'editoria indipendente italiana	Publishing Industry	Attended	Networking / dissemination	Milan	Thousands of people attend the fair	DEN
17	6/5/2022	6/5/2022	FEP Meetings	Publishing Industry	Organised	Recruitment of people, platform, script	Munich	36	FEP
18	10/05/2022	13/05/2022	Integrated Systems Europe (ISE) 2022	Media Industry	Attended	Booth	Barcelona	43.000	EUT
19	5/19/2022	5/19/2022	Salone del Libro	Publishing Industry	Attended	Networking / dissemination	Turin	341,000 visitors in 2015	DEN
20	5/20/2022	5/20/2022	NEM SB Meeting	ICT Sector	Attended	Networking/ Dissemination	Brussels	30	IN2
21	7/06/2022	10/06/2022	Future Week Bergen	Media Ecosystem,	Attended	Panel	Bergen	2.000	EUT, FMWC
22	10/06/2022	10/06/2022	ICT-44 meeting Bergen	Media Industry	Co-organised (sibling projects)	Close meeting	Bergen	8	EUT, FMWC
23	14/06/2022	16/06/2022	Young publishing professionals in Belgium	Publishing Industry	Organised	Recruitment of people, platform, script	Brussels	27	FEP
24	7/9/2022	9/9/2022	Ars Electronica	All Stakeholders	Attended	Möbius presentation	Linz	71.000	FMWC

25	21/09/2022	23/09/2022	Open Living Labs Days 2022	All stakeholders	Organised	Möbius Booth + piloting	Turin	300	ENoLL
26	23/09/2022	23/09/2022	FEP Meetings	Publishing Industry	Organised	Close d meeting	Riga	30	FEP
27	19/10/2022	23/10/2022	Frankfurt Book Fair 2022	All Stakeholders	Attended	Booth + Pilotin g	Frankfurt	160.000	MVB, FMWC, IMEC
28	21/10/2022	21/10/2022	STARTS Day – Frankfurt Book Fair 2022	Publishing Industry, policy and society	Organised	Prese ntatio n	Frankfurt	25	MVB, EUT, DEN, FMWC
29	29/11/2022	29/11/2022	Policy-making Workshop 2022	All Stakeholder s	Organised	Round table	Online	46	FMWC, DEN, FEP, IN2
30	1/2/2023	1/2/2023	Integrated Systems Europe (ISE) 2023	Media Industry	Attended	Booth	Barcelona	58.000	Eurecat
31	27/02/2023	02/03/2023	Mobile World Congress 2023	ICT Sector	Attended	Round table	Barcelona	2.400 (at the booth)	FMWC, MVB, IN2, DEN
32	10/03/2023	12/03/2023	Book Pride Milano 2023	Publishing Industry	Attended	Booth	Milan	18.300	Bookabook, FMWC
33	13/03/2023	13/03/2023	FEP Meeting	Publishing Industry	Organised	Close d meeti ng	Online	34	FEP
34	18/04/2023	20/04/2023	London Book Fair 2023	Publishing Industry, Prosumer sector	Attended	Booth + pilotin g	London	30.000 / 56 Player, 6 Creator, 3 PIT	FMWC, ENoLL
35	27/04/2023	30/04/2023	Leipzig Book Fair 2023	Publishing Industry, Prosumer sector	Attended	Booth + pilotin g	Leipzig	274.000	KKW, All
36	29/04/2023	29/04/2023	Möbius Fantastic Adventure Night	General Public	Organised	Vernis sage	Leipzig	150	KKW, All
37	18/05/2023	22/05/2023	Salone del Libro di Torino 2023	Publishing Industry, Prosumer sector	Attended	Booth + pilotin g	Turin	215.000/ 58 Player, 7 Creator, 9 PIT	ENoLL
38	30/05/2023	30/05/2023	EIT Culture &	Policy and Society	Attended	Netwo rking	Brussels	50	DEN

			Creativity Moonshot Event.						
39	7/6/2023	7/6/2023	Readmagine Madrid	Publishing sector, Academia, Policy and Society	Organised	Workshop + networking	Madrid	20	IMEC, FEP, FMWC
40	8/6/2023	8/6/2023	Media Futures Event - Hamburg	Research, ICT Sector	Attended	Presentation	Hamburg	50	FMWC, DEN
41	15/06/2023	15/06/2023	FEP Meeting	Publishing Industry	Organised	Close Meeting	Paris	43	FEP
42	27/07/2023	27/07/2023	Workshop: Let's test the Möbius Creator I	Publishing Industry	Organised	Workshop	Online	33	IMEC, DEN, FMWC
43	3/8/2023	3/8/2023	Workshop: Let's test the Möbius Creator II	Publishing Industry	Organised	Workshop	Online	12	IMEC, DEN, FMWC
44	15/09/2023	18/09/2023	IBC Amsterdam 2023	ICT Sector	Attended	Booth + pilotin g	Amsterdam	43.065	FMWC, IMEC, DEN, IN2
45	21/09/2023	23/09/2023	Open Living Lab Days 2023	All stakeholders	Organised	Booth + pilotin g	Barcelona	400+/5 Player, 2 Creator	ENoLL
46	04/10/2023	06/10/2023	Liber Madrid 2023	Publishing Industry, Prosumer sector	Attended	Booth + pilotin g	Madrid	9.235/44 Player, 12 Creator, 10 PIT	ENoLL
47	11/10/2023	11/10/2023	Möbius Vernissage in Leipzig	General Public	Organised	Show case	Leipzig	70	KKW
48	12/10/2023	15/10/2023	Bright Festival Connect 2023	General Public	Organised	Show case	Leipzig	2.655	KKW
49	18/10/2023	22/10/2023	Frankfurt Book Fair 2023	All Stakeholders	Attended	Booth + pilotin g	Frankfurt	105.000	MVB, DEN, IN2, FMWC, KKW, EUT, BB, IMEC, FEP
50	18/10/2023	18/10/2023	Preliminary Results Panel – FBF 2023	All stakeholders	Organised	Presentatio n	Frankfurt	30	DEN, IN2, FMWC, MVB, KKW, EUT, BB, IMEC, FEP

51	19/10/2023	19/10/2023	Policy-event on cross-sectoriality – FBF 2023	Policy and Society	Organised	Round table	Frankfurt	21	DEN, IN2, FMWC, MVB, KKW, EUT, IMEC
52	20/10/2023	20/10/2023	Workshop to test the PIT - FBF 2023	Publishing Industry, Prosumer sector	Organised	Workshop	Frankfurt	1	DEN, IN2, FMWC, MVB, IMEC
53	08/11/2023	12/11/2023	Vienna Book Fair 2023	Publishing Industry, Prosumer sector	Attended	Booth + piloting	Vienna	20.000 / 31 Player, 7 Creator, 6 VR Experience	ENoLL
54	13/11/2023	14/11/2023	FEP Meetings	Publishing Industry	Organised	Close Meeting	Brussels	35	FEP
55	21/11/2023	26/11/2023	Ljubljana Book Fair 2023	Publishing Industry, Prosumer sector	Attended	Booth + piloting	Ljubljana	30.000 / 3 Player, 3 Creator, 56 VR Experience	ENoLL
56	26/02/2024	29/02/2024	Mobile World Congress Barcelona	ICT Sector	Attended	Booth + piloting	Barcelona		FMWC, All
57	23.05.2023	25.05.2023	Infoshare Gdansk	General Public	Attended	Physically	Gdansk, Poland	5 Player	KPT
58	03.06.2023	18.07.2023	Piloting Activity - internal & external meetings including Social Innovations Demo Days, #SDG48h Challenge 16th June & Summer Jan Event on 4th July	All stakeholders	Attended	Physically and online	-	17 Player	KPT
59	19.07.2023	31.07.2023	Piloting Activity - internal & external meetings	All stakeholders	Attended	Physically and online	-	49 Player	KPT

60	01.08.2023	31.08.2023	Piloting Activity - internal & external meetings	All stakeholders	Attended	Physically and online	-	34 Player	KPT
61	01.09.2023	30.09.2023	Piloting Activity - internal & external meetings	All stakeholders	Attended	Physically and online	-	16 Player, 4 Creator	KPT
62	01.10.2023	31.10.2023	Piloting Activity - internal & external meetings including International Book Fair in Krakow October 26-29	All stakeholders	Attended	Physically and online	-	53 Player, 6 Creator	KPT
63	12/06/2023	15/06/2023	ACM IMX	All stakeholders	Attended	Presentation	Nantes	70-80	IMEC
64	27/01/2022	27/01/2022	Co-creation Session (Workshop)	Publishers	Organised	Online	Online	6	Imec/ MVB
65	03/03/2022	03/03/2022	Co-creation Session (Workshop)	Prosumers (readers, general public)	Organised	Online	Online	4	Imec/ ENOLL/ MVB
66	28.01.2022	28.01.2022	<u>Think-aloud-session (Workshop - several appointments coordinated by imec)</u>	Publishers	Organised	Online	Online	5	Imec/ MVB
67	21.02.2022	28.02.2022	Interview	Publishers	organised	online	Online	2	IMEC/MVB
68	24.02.2022	24.02.2022	Co-creation session	Writers/authors	Organised	Online	Online	7	BOOKABOOK/ENOLL
69	25.02.2022	25.02.2022	Co-creation session	Writers/authors	organised	online	Online	6	Eurecat/ENOLL

70	14/02/2022	14/02/2022	Co-creation session	Readers	Organised	Online	Online	8	Imec/ MVB
71	21.02.2022	21.02.2022	Co-creation session	Readers	organised	Online	Online	6	Imec/ MVB
72	11/02/2021	11/02/2021	Piloting activity (Workshop)	Prosumers (readers, general public)	Organised	Online	Online	Not provided by the partner	ENoLL
73	30/01/2024	01/02/2024	ISE 2024	Media Industry	Attended	Booth	Spain	Not provided by the partner	Eurecat

Table 6: List of attended events

In the table above, the overall number of the attendees has been added, however it is worth mentioning that at the events where the Möbius project had a booth, since it didn't have a precise application to scan and count each visitor, the only possible shareable number is related to the feedback received in the events where piloting activities took place. Therefore, these events have two numbers: the overall and the participants in the piloting activities.

10.1.7 Social Media

In the current dynamic digital landscape, Möbius has leveraged the power of social media platforms such as [X](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Instagram](#), and [YouTube](#) to connect and engage with its target audience effectively. Social media has revolutionised communication, constantly evolving to offer new tools and opportunities for reaching and connecting with identified stakeholders. Instagram has been employed for engaging the audience and as a content repository, without the pressures of what was up to date. The YouTube channel, on the other hand, has served as an essential hub for sharing insightful videos and updates. These platforms have facilitated communicating and disseminating valuable information among the project's target audience.

Figure 8: Screenshot of Möbius LinkedIn account

Figure 9: Screenshot of Möbius Twitter account

Figure 10: Screenshot of Möbius Instagram account

10.1.7.1. Social media strategy

The social media strategy is based on the cooperation of the three kinds of media:

- **Owned social media:** there are three active social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram). The presence to this social media is necessary to extend the brand in the digital ecosystem.
- **Shared social media:** This refers to social media accounts that do not have the Möbius name on them, but that nevertheless will be used to share relevant content, for example the partner’s social media channels.
- **Earned social media:** Refers to coverage achieved due to public, blogger and influencer relations efforts, for example, online word of mouth, ‘viral’ tendencies, mentions, shares, reviews and reposts. The supportive communities of Möbius and other partner networks help to spread the information published by the official accounts.

Social Media	Followers	Impressions
LinkedIn	964	(see the screenshot below)
Twitter	327	+430K
Instagram	196	N/A

Table 7: Social media general overview

Twitter (X)

Regarding the owned social media, the X account has **327** followers and has posted **842** tweets. *From March 2021 to October 2022 there is no data about Twitter impressions because the social media per se has erased them with the change of its company owner.*

MONTH	Impressions	New followers
Mar. 2021	N/A	10
Apr. 2021	N/A	18
May 2021	N/A	2
Jun. 2021	N/A	7

Jul, 2021	N/A	3
Aug. 2021	N/A	1
Sept. 2021	N/A	2
Oct. 2021	N/A	0
Nov. 2021	N/A	3
Dec. 2021	N/A	6
Jan. 2022	N/A	9
Feb. 2022	N/A	4
Mar. 2022	N/A	4
April 2022	N/A	2
May 2022	N/A	2
June 2022	N/A	0
July 2022	N/A	7
Aug. 2022	N/A	0
Sept. 2022	N/A	6
Oct. 2022	N/A	9
Nov. 2022	2.509	12
Dec. 2022	3.891	2
Jan. 2023	674	-1
Feb. 2023	1.116	-1
Mar. 2023	10.6K	4
Apr. 2023	399K	175
May 2023	1.754	3

Jun. 2023	1.409	-1
Jul. 2023	1.557	-4
Aug. 2023	2.089	-1
Sep. 2023	1.727	8
Oct. 2023	2.183	9
Nov. 2023	1.286	0
Dec. 2023	647	0
Jan. 2024	707	1
Feb. 2024	798	0

Table 8: X metrics table

LinkedIn Followers

The LinkedIn page has 964 followers. The increasing number of followers on the channel shows that the actions taken to promote the page and its contents have worked. Events' participation is the engagement motor for the page. The number of followers increases after each project presentation or activity at fairs. This can be seen in the peaks of spring (March, April, and May 2023) and autumn (September, October, and November 2023). 682 new followers have been reached in the past year, 340 organically and 342 through a paid campaign.

Figure 11: Number of the Möbius LinkedIn account followers

LinkedIn Impressions

The organic impressions (impressions achieved without paid actions) maintained a stable level during the past year (Nov 2022 to Nov 2023), with an increase from September to November 2023 due to the project's attendance at events such as the Frankfurt Book Fair Thus, more than 33k impressions have been achieved organically, and through the paid campaign (ongoing from September 2022 to February 2024), more than 309k impressions.

Figure 12: Impressions of Möbius LinkedIn account

LinkedIn Visitor Type of Industry

The top three visitors are from the following sectors: telecommunications (9,5%), IT (9%), and publishers (8,7%). Find more details in the infographic below:

Figure 13: Möbius LinkedIn visitors industry

Instagram Analytics

Since the Instagram account has been used as a repository of images without being updated with the same calendarisation as Twitter or LinkedIn, the number of followers has not been boosted equally. However, the numbers have been increasing either way, but slower.

Figure 14: Möbius Instagram overview and followers analytics

Shared social media

Figure 15: Shared Social Media

Earned social media

Figure 16: Earned Social Media

Paid campaigns

Möbius launched two different paid campaigns to increase the engagement, and the number of followers of the project’s social media accounts. The first paid campaign was launched before the kick-off of Phase 3a of the project. Partners attended many book, technological, and media fairs during this phase. The marketing company Skyrocket contribute to reach 93 followers and to increase engagement in Twitter and LinkedIn between March 2023 to April 2023.

Objetivo	Impresiones	Gasto	Inicio de la campaña	Finalización de la campaña	Presupuesto total	Resultados	Tipo de resultado	Tasa de resultado	Costo por resultado	CPA
Seguidores	161.162	89,97 €	06-Apr-2023 10:34	13-Apr-2023 23:30	100,00 €	59	Seguimientos	0,04%	1,52 €	20,00 €
Seguidores	96.802	50,00 €	31-Mar-2023 13:20	07-Apr-2023 00:00	50,00 €	34	Seguimientos	0,04%	1,43 €	8,50 €

Table 9: Skyrocket report March to April 2023

Phase 3b of the project was launched in September, and a wide range of events were about to occur. Another paid campaign was launched with Imagina Digital to increase the metrics of LinkedIn and the project's impact. As appreciated in the LinkedIn metrics above, the engagement (impressions) and followers increased when the paid campaign was activated. The same strategy has not been applied to X or Instagram. In the case of X, extra payment policies were requested to activate a paid campaign. A verified account on the platform costs

1000\$ per month. This expense was not contemplated. On Instagram, it was impossible to start a paid campaign due to Meta policies. Nonetheless, as appreciated in the LinkedIn metrics above, the engagement (impressions) and the followers increased during the period the paid campaign was active.

Figure 17: Imagina Digital report

The paid campaign with Imagina Digital started at the end of September by boosting posts from upcoming events, such as Liber Madrid 2023, but mostly the ones about the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023. Since the engagement and the followers were not increasing as expected, a post with a brief explanation of the project and a video was also published, besides boosting separate posts with key moments or advancements. This post has exponentially increased the engagement and followers of the project's LinkedIn account. The paid campaign ended the 14th of February of 2024, thus having promoted the Möbius Closing Event at MWC24 as well.

Figure 18: LinkedIn Paid Campaign

Social media overall KPIs

Our efforts to achieve the social media KPIs for the overall Möbius accounts reached **1.465** followers. Several factors contributed to this outcome. Firstly, the publishing sector is highly niche, limiting the project’s potential audience size. Secondly, being cross-sectoral, Möbius faced difficulties in tackling a diverse range of interests and demographics. Lastly, the Möbius sibling projects (Stadium, MediaVerse, Copa Europe) encountered similar challenges, resulting in comparable follower counts. Despite this, FMWC remained committed to refining the strategy, engaging the existing followers, and exploring new avenues to grow the audience. Thus, FMWC used Scrab.in, a platform to send one-on-one messages to the LinkedIn targeted audience, paid campaigns, newsletters, the website, and offline attendance at events.

10.1.8 Newsletter

A newsletter was issued every three months **to communicate highlights and push out announcements of interest to all target stakeholders**. the quarterly digest contained news items about the project’s activities and work, self-created blog articles by all Möbius partners, event participation, and open calls.

The newsletter is an essential part of the lead generation strategy of the project. Its main goal was to increase awareness of the Möbius communication channels and become a dynamic reminder to the targeted audience of all the information about Möbius (open calls, new technology information, events, etc.).

The design has used the project's brand identity, and it has a look and feel according to the Möbius website. Newsletters usually follow the same structure. There are some sections fixed present in all the newsletters:

1. Opening with one or more highlights of the project
2. Check our insights!
3. Our Ecosystem
4. Upcoming Events

The platform the project has been using for sending the newsletters has been Mailchimp, which raised upon **350 subscribers**. Twelve official newsletters were sent to the audience. However, the platform has been also used to contact them for eleven different reminders about exciting events that Möbius was participating in or organising or to apply to the Möbius Open Call.

In January 2024, Möbius reached 350 contacts on its database, 314 of them, subscribers. Through the past year, a stable database of subscribers has been maintained and it has improved the open rate in the last newsletters. The average open rate 38% is and the average click rate is 3,58%.

To increase the number of newsletter subscribers and recipients list, an online campaign was deployed by embedding a visible call-to-action button on the website (with a **pop up** for new visitors to the website asking to subscribe to the Möbius newsletter), and a **social media campaign** via relevant content sharing was launched. Furthermore, the **newsletter link was shared as posts on the Möbius social media channels**. Offline actions (direct invitation) at events were also deployed to increase the number of subscribers to the newsletter.

Figure 19: Subscribe to our Newsletter Communication Campaign

Mailchimp Official Newsletters

Title	Date	No	Objective	Recipients sent	Link
Möbius First Newsletter	28.06.21	1	Share the Möbius website and the first blogposts, present the ecosystem	27	link
Mobius Open Call is officially launched!	16.12.21	2	Launch the Open Call for manuscripts, share new content of the website	1.364	link

#1 Möbius 2022 Newsletter Data on the recently closed Open Call	21.02.22	3	Share data about the closed open call	1.376	link
#2 Möbius 2022 Newsletter Möbius Awards Ceremony	31.03.22	4	Invitation of the Möbius Awards Ceremony	1.362	link
#3 Möbius 2022 Newsletter Meet the Winners of the Open Call	18.05.22	5	Meet the winners of the open call	1.344	link
#4 Möbius 2022 Newsletter Möbius is at the Frankfurt Bookfair!	20.10.22	6	Möbius attendance at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2022	148	link
#5 Möbius 2022 Newsletter Come to the Möbius Policy Workshop!	24.11.22	7	Invitation and information about the Möbius policy event	151	link
#1 Möbius 2023 Newsletter	20.02.23	8	Info about the MWC23 in Barcelona and new insights in the Möbius Website	160	link
#2 Möbius 2023 Newsletter	13.04.23	9	Information about the Fantastic Night in Leipzig in the frame of the Leipzig Book Fair 2023	169	link
#3 Möbius 2023 Newsletter	07.06.23	10	Möbius summary of the past events (London, Leipzig, Turin) and invitation to Readmagine workshop in Madrid	192	link
#4 Möbius 2023 Newsletter	29.09.23	11	Möbius participation in IBC Amsterdam and Agenda for the Möbius Closing Event in the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023	288	link
#5 Möbius 2023 Newsletter	31/10/2023	12	Recap of the multiple events where Möbius participated in October, focus on the Frankfurter Buchmesse.	296	link

MÖBIUS NEWSLETTER

Möbius is presenting the Prosumers Intelligence Toolkit today at Readmagine 2023!

Möbius at Readmagine 2023

Workshop

The Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit: A tool to understand how readers interact with books

7 June - 17:15h
Casa del Lector - Madrid

#mobiustobook mobiustoolkit.eu

🗓️ Are you attending the **Readmagine 2023** event **today** in Madrid?

👋 The Möbius Project is!

Don't miss our workshop **"The Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit: A tool to understand how readers interact with books"** with Elias Blanckaert and Enrico Turrin.

They will explain to you how the PIT, a **data dashboard for publishers** that presents insights by collecting knowledge and data from prosumer online fandom communities, works.

🕒 **7 June at 17:15h - this afternoon!!**

📍 Casa del Lector, Madrid.

Register for free here

Möbius showcased and tested its innovative applications for the first time at the London Book Fair 2023!

Figure 20: Mailchimp newsletter format

Mailchimp reminders:

No	Title	Date	Recipients sent	Link
1	Möbius_manuscripts ADV ITA	23.11.21	1.332	link
2	Come to test the Mobius Creator!	19.09.22	146	link
3	Come to visit Mobius at the Frankfurt Book Fair!	03.10.22	147	link
4	Join us at the Mobius policy workshop!	09.11.22	150	link
5	Join us at the online workshops to test the Möbius Creator!	11.07.23	199	link

6	Reminder - Join us at the online workshops to test the Möbius Creator!	19.07.23	205	link
7	Reminder - Online workshop to test the Möbius Creator 3 August!	02.08.23	206	link
8	IBC2023 - Free tickets	12.09.23	286	link
9	Reminder 2 - Online workshop to test the Möbius Creator 2 October!	02.10.23	285	link
10	Reminder - Frankfurt Book Fair 2023!	16.10.23	296	link

Table 10: List of Mailchimp reminders

Figure 21: Möbius Mailchimp Newsletters reminders

Despite the use and the effectiveness of this tool, FMWC team detected that LinkedIn had a newsletter service that was very productive. By M30 of the project, with the main purpose of leading and increasing Möbius' visibility according to the strategy, a LinkedIn newsletter was opened for the project, which has been sent monthly for six months and reached 190

subscribers. The format of this newsletter was adapted to Mailchimp to keep the subscribers of this platform alive, but the content was distributed differently. It had the shape of an article mentioning and linking the last celebrated Möbius activity each month and the ones about to come.

October Digest: The Möbius Immersive Storytelling Adventures

 Möbius
565 seguidores

2 de noviembre de 2023

[Abrir lector interactivo](#)

October has been a month filled with multiple events, during which Möbius actively participated in delivering immersive storytelling experiences and embracing innovation. In this newsletter we invite you to take a closer look at our eventful month.

Testing Innovation at OpenLivingLab Days

In Barcelona, Möbius participated in the [2023 OpenLivingLab Days](#), a dynamic event hosted by the [European Network of Living Labs \(ENoLL\)](#) and local living labs. Our project demonstrated its transformative potential during the **third Phase of the Pilots**, captivating innovation enthusiasts from around the world to take part in our piloting activities.

Figure 22: Möbius LinkedIn Newsletter format

LinkedIn Newsletters

No	Title	Date	Objective	Impress.	Subscribers at each time
1	Immersive reading is the	28/09/2023	Recap of the Möbius participation in the IBC event in Amsterdam and the launch of the	90	146

	new trend in publishing		showcasing of the VR headsets experience.		
2	October Digest: The Möbius Immersive Storytelling Adventures	02/11/2023	Recap on the events that Möbius attended during October, especial focus on the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023.	133	199
3	November Digest: Möbius Monthly highlights	01/12/2023	Recap on the events that Möbius attended during November and a special mention to the wrap up videos from the Frankfurt Buchmesse.	117	358
4	December Digest: Möbius Monthly Highlights	29/12/2023	Happy holidays wish and a brief remember about the Möbius Interviews to the partner during the Frankfurt Buchmesse.	285	406
5	January Digest: Möbius Monthly Highlights	02/02/2024	A Möbius Closing Event at MWC24 reminder and recap of the previous attendance at events	63	415
6	February Digest:	To be sent	To be sent	To be sent	To be sent

Table 11: List of LinkedIn Newsletters sent

10.1.9 Scientific Publications

Scientific Publications with significant impact factors have been listed to communicate about the results of the research.

Partner	Title	Publication	Date
IMEC / DEN	The Role of Prosumer in Reshaping the Publishing	Springer	21-Jan-22

	Industry: Preliminary Findings from the Möbius Project.		
IMEC	"De kracht van de 'prosumer': digitale innovatie voor uitgevers in Europa"	Tijdschrift van de communicatiewetenschap	Rejected but presented during the at 'Etmaal van de communicatiewetenschap'
IMEC	On-going	To be published	TBC
EUT	On-going	To be published	TBC

Table 11: List of publications and conferences

The Möbius consortium has created and published content, including scientific articles, public deliverables, and flyers, roll-ups and one-pagers on Zenodo, an open-access platform. It is aligned to the project's commitment to transparency, knowledge sharing, and the broader dissemination of the project's outcomes. By making the materials openly accessible on Zenodo, Möbius ensures that the research findings and resources are readily available to a global audience, including fellow researchers, practitioners, and the general public. This not only enhances the visibility and impact of the work done but also fosters collaboration and knowledge exchange within the wider scientific and creative communities. Additionally, utilizing an open-access platform like Zenodo reinforces the project's dedication to promoting open science principles and advancing the accessibility of research, contributing to the greater good of the research ecosystem.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo website interface. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. Below the search bar, the Möbius logo and the tagline 'The power of prosumers in publishing' are visible. The main content area displays search results for '7 results found', sorted by 'Newest'. Two results are shown:

- D3.5 Final Report on Prosumer Business Models, cross-sector scalability and IP Framework** by IMEC, dated December 1, 2023 (v1). The description states: "This defines the principal conditions for fair and sustainable cooperation with prosumer communities and cross-sectoral scalability analysis. It concludes the work done in T3.3 'Prosumer business models and cross-sectoral scalability' and T3.4 'Application of IP framework to prosumer business models' of the Möbius project. It builds upon the ins...".
- D1.4. Initial Data Management Plan** by Eureka, dated August 31, 2021 (v1). The description states: "This document is the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of Möbius project. The DMP includes all the preliminary information regarding data management, this is information on datasets collected, produced, and processed within the project for management and research purposes. The DMP is based on the FAIR (findable, accessible, inter...".

Figure 23: Möbius Zenodo's Community

11. Open Call for Manuscripts

The Möbius Open Call for Manuscripts, which ran from November 8, 2021, to January 15, 2022, was a collaborative effort between the consortium. Bookabook led the open call, and Mobile World Capital Barcelona coordinated the communication and dissemination. This initiative aimed to engage and discover talented writers and their works and, more specifically, to collect prosumers' works upon which to create the Möbius book, together with the one based on Bookabook's bestseller *The Influence of Blue*, EUT and Bookabook, as leaders of WP4 and T4.2, established the rules. Manuscripts should be original and unpublished, should have a maximum length of 6.000 characters – in order to receive complete stories that could be transformed into a 6-minute audiobook production – and should be in English, Italian or Spanish. The language criterion was set because, in both organizations, personnel involved in the project are proficient in all three languages. This strategy has also benefitted the open call to maximize subscriptions in languages other than English. Moreover, it was decided that author(s) – citizens and residents of EU-27 countries, plus associated countries or in the process of becoming associated with Horizon Europe, over 18 years old – may submit a maximum of two manuscripts. MWCcapital took the lead in orchestrating the call's communication strategy, including the information on the website and social media activities to maximize the outreach. A communication campaign was designed and executed to attract potential applicants.

A targeted marketing campaign was launched through Möbius' Instagram and Mailchimp accounts in collaboration with Bookabook and MVB, using their respective datasets and other platforms, such as the Spanish escritores.org. The entire campaign was conducted under the guidance of the project's legal advisor from IMEC.

The Möbius Open Call for Manuscripts saw participation from 175 talented persons MWCcapital developed an informative infographic to give an overview of the outcomes of the Open Call. Additionally, an online Möbius Awards Ceremony was organised to announce and honour the winners. Prizes (Möbius 3d printed trophy) were sent to the first, second, and third-place winners. Following the awards ceremony, interviews were conducted online with each of the winning authors, providing valuable insights into their creative processes. A dedicated webpage showcased the submitted manuscripts so readers and enthusiasts could explore the works. This dedicated page was promoted across the different social media channels and the Möbius newsletter.

Figure 24: Screenshot of the Möbius Winners' webpage

After the closure of the Open Call, the webpage was updated to provide a historical perspective, a direct link to the Möbius Awards Ceremony and a button to access the Winners' webpage.

Figure 25: Screenshot of the updated Closed Open Call Webpage

12. Exploitation activities and results

This exploitation section will elucidate the strategic initiatives and methodology undertaken within the Möbius project for the comprehensive exploitation of its outcomes.

Built upon deliverable D6.2 and as a result of the application of the methodology, the Möbius Exploitable Results (ERs) will be presented in a dedicated section. T6.2 has been led by MVB and has counted with the support of EUT and FMWC, counting on the involvement of all partners.

The different exploitation outcomes have been updated continuously in a living document in the Möbius SharePoint also including the identification of IP claims and ownership. Moreover, the different results have been prioritized into Key Exploitable Results (KERs). Exploitation roadmaps considering also the IPR management strategy for the main Möbius KERs have been designed and further characterized. The complete business plan/s is included in deliverable D6.5.

12.1 Möbius exploitation methodology

The **exploitation of results** in a European Project is crucial when it comes to creating positive externalities and impact of the Research and Development (R&D) Activities. Beyond the scope

of the project, it ensures that the outcomes derived from a collaboration between organisations get to the market and to the interested target groups.

The approach followed by MVB and EUT to define the Exploitable Results of the Möbius project has consisted of a **3-steps process**.

Figure 26: 3-steps exploitation approach

The first step has been the **definition of the results**, listing in a shared document the initial expected list forms the proposal and updating them with partners to reflect the final outcomes generated throughout the project.

After, the second step has included the identification of Intellectual Property (IP) Claims consisting in the identification of background (Consortium Agreement) and foreground of the project.

Finally, once the ERs had been defined including their IP claims, the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of the project were selected and next to the involved partners, the exploitation roadmaps were designed and will be found in this deliverable.

The previous ERs tables included in D6.2 (M24) have been updated during the last months to represent a definitive outlook of the project outcomes that consider all the significant synergies and developments that have taken place in Möbius.

This final validation of results has been carried out by MVB and EUT through individual meetings with each project partner, in which the living document was reviewed, and changes were made. At all times, the changes were tracked and in the SharePoint document to allow reviews by other partners and avoid IPR conflicts, ensuring a transparent process.

12.2 The Möbius Exploitable Results (ERs) - Step 1

The **Möbius Exploitable Results (ER)** have been clustered into **6 results** and **24 sub-results**. This clustering has responded to the purpose of specifying the contributions of each project partner in case of jointly owned results, as many of the project outcomes are results of the integration of the work of several project partners, that can be both exploited as final products and individually (e.g., a literary work). The categories of the the **30 Möbius results and subresults aggregated** are mainly:

- 6 Softwares

- 3 Products
- 2 Procedures
- 11 Know-how
- 6 Methodologies/toolkits
- 1 Literary work
- 1 Code framework

As in D6.2, partners have also defined the **time-to-market** of the result, the **resources and investment needed** after the project end to take the results to the market, the **foreseen IPR protection** to be applied and the **partners involved**. The **target groups** for the results were studied together in the Business Clinic Workshops, thus they have already been included in D6.2 in the debriefings of the workshops.

Figure 27: Möbius 6 main Exploitable Results (ER)

SCIENTIFIC CONTRIBUTION OF THE MÖBIUS PROJECT

The Möbius project has continuously contributed to the scientific body of knowledge throughout the project. The main topics of research of the Möbius research partners have extended from the exploration of the copyright implications of prosumer business models to the user requirements for immersive reading tools. Mainly, the results that are going to be disseminated as part of the project scientific contribution that can have replicability in future EU projects are methodologies and toolkits, know-how and procedures.

Möbius Methodologies and Toolkits (ER1, ER1.2, ER1.4, ER1.7.1, 1.7.2):

ER1 introduces the Möbius framework and methodologies, streamlining cooperation in publishing value chains, which is a valuable contribution to understanding the dynamics of prosumer engagement and cross-sectoral collaboration.

ER1.1 and ER1.2 developed by DEN delve into **impact assessment methodologies**, providing insights into the social, economic, and technological impacts of Möbius outputs. These methodologies can be instrumental in evaluating similar projects in the future.

ER2 developed by IN2 and EUT is a software toolkit that is able to analyse and present key data about prosumers and their works.

E1.4 developed by IN2 in collaboration with EUT represents the integrated Möbius application (web and mobile) for creating and experiencing immersive Möbius books. This is a key exploitable outcome whose business plan is described in more detail in D6.5

ER1.7 contributes a long-term roadmap and business plan methodology, aiding in the innovation and exploitation potential assessment of Möbius results led by MVB and EUT, furthering the understanding of business models in the prosumer context.

Know-How (ER1.1, ER1.5, ER1.7, ER2.2, ER3.1, ER3.2, ER3.4, ER4.2, ER4.6, ER6):

These ERs offer diverse forms of knowledge, ranging from user requirements for immersive reading tools to legal advice on prosumer business models and copyright implications. Collectively, they enrich the understanding of legal and user-oriented aspects of the prosumer and publishing landscape.

ER1.5 and ER2.2TA provide insights into skill development and applicability of Möbius system requirements, ensuring relevance and usability.

ER4.6 focuses on dissemination and communication strategies, which can contribute to the dissemination of knowledge about the Möbius project itself.

Procedures (ER1.3, ER1.6):

ER1.3 offers protocols for workshops, enabling practical insights into organizing collaborative events. The comparative analysis of different setups and participants contributes to the understanding of effective workshop organization.

The outcomes of these scientific contributions are expected to be disseminated through publications in scientific papers and sectorial journals, with a focus on medium-term exploitation.

ER1.6 establishing steps and constitutes internal know-how obtained by the FMWC in order to manage dissemination and communication activities in the publishing sector.

TECHNICAL CONTRIBUTION OF THE MÖBIUS PROJECT

The Möbius project made significant technical contributions to enhance the immersive reading experience, involving the development of a set of software tools enabling cross-media immersive book experiences. Key contributions in the technical aspect have been the Möbius Creator Toolkit and the Möbius Player developed by IN2. Other technical contributions developed are the spatializer software and the alignment tool led by EUT, enhancing the reading experience by providing audio enhancements and interactive capabilities.

In technical and cultural terms, the Möbius Immersive Book Box and experimental cross-media productions have also demonstrated the possibilities of immersive reading experiences for individual and social consumption.

N	ER	Category	WPs	Value proposition	Time-to-market	Resources and investment needed	Partners involved	IPR foreseen protection
ER1	Möbius framework and methodologies	Methodology / toolkit	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	Achieve streamlining meaningful, fair and sustainable cooperation with prosumers and cross-sectoral stakeholders through publishing value chains, including empirical assessment of social, economic and technological impacts.	1 year	Onboarding sectoral stakeholders would be needed.	FMWC, imec-SMIT, DEN, ENOLL, MVB, EUT	Copyright
ER1.1	Main evidence based on the Impact assessment of the Möbius KER	Know-how	WP2	This study will provide knowledge on the kind of impact (social, economic, technological) achieved by the three Möbius outputs (PIT, player, creator) during the assessment conducted in the three pilots. The results will allow us to understand how Möbius proposition and innovation impacts on the publishing sector.	1 year	Publishing the results on scientific papers or sectorial journals. Medium-term exploitation (publications after the project end).	DEN	Open access

ER1.2	Impact assessment methodology	Methodology / toolkit	WP2	Definition of a methodology to assess the impact of innovation in publishing sector that can be further validated in the future	1 year	Further scientific research to guarantee ongoing implementation and adjustment of the framework. Consultancy services (possibility to adapt the results). Expand the sector of work (private and public subjects).	DEN	Open access
ER1.3	Protocols for the workshops carried out to validate the project results	Procedure	WP5	Lessons learnt on the practical organisation of workshops based on the methodology designed by IMEC. Including comparative analysis considering different setups and participants: online involvement of participants, cross-country workshops, etc.	Imminent	Further scientific research to guarantee ongoing implementation and adjustment of the framework. Other European projects, new lines of research. Expand the sector of work (other immersive experiences).	ENOLL, IMEC-Smit, FMWC	No IPR protection applied
ER1.4	User requirements know-how as a baseline for immersive reading developments	Methodology / Know-how	WP2, WP5	User requirements gathered during workshops with end-users to help technology developers in new immersive reading tools	Imminent	Further scientific research to guarantee ongoing implementation and adjustment of the framework. Other European projects, new lines of research. Expand the sector of work (other immersive experiences).	IMEC-SMIT	Open access

ER1.5	Knowledge on Möbius system requirements and relevant use-cases	Know-how	WP2	Skills development and experimental issues to create meaningful systems for living labs (T2.3)	Imminent	Other european projects.	IN2	Copyright
ER1.6	Know-how on managing dissemination and communication activities in the publishing sector	Procedure	WP6	Know-how that can be useful to facilitate the creation of impact by the FMWC in other European projects	Imminent	Other european projects and european level dissemination activities	FMWC	No IPR protection applied
ER1.7	Long Term Roadmap / Business Plan Methodology	Know-How	WP6	Methodology built within the Möbius project to explore the innovation and exploitation potential of the project result to define a business plan for 4 KER (Creator, Player, PIT and möbius box)	Imminent	Business Planning / Marketing / Sales / Controlling / Legal Advisory	MVB / EURECAT	Copyright (?)
ER2	Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT)	Toolkit	WP3	Extract actionable knowledge from user bases and communities of interest	1 year	Marketing, sales, onboarding, IT support, product dev, legal, consulting (to set-up algorithms and metrics to be used, adapt dashboards, etc..); most importantly it will be necessary to secure the underlying data to be used by the PIT; potential to be used beyond fan fiction communities (for example, for social media)	IN2, EUT, imec-SMIT, FEP, MVB	Copyright

ER2.1	Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT) - Fan-fiction community metrics	Framework, Code	WP3	Provide valuable information regarding the fan-fiction community and understand the community interests and dynamics. Value added to publishers and communities.	1 year	Engineering the data processing pipeline (automatisation)	EUT	Open Source Code, copyright (publications)
ER 2.2	User Experience and applicability to the publishing sector	Know-how	WP3	Increase of the possibility of the PIT to be relevant in the publishing sector	Imminent	Any resources nor investment needed	FEP, MVB	No IPR protection applied
ER2.3	Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT) - Software/User interface (frontend and backend) for community metrics visualization	Software	WP2	Dashboard with many applications for the publishing sector, it allows the visualisation of any data that needs to be visualize and correlated	2 years	Develop the demo-site with live data.	IN2	Copyright

ER3	Möbius prosumer business models	Know-how	WP3	Carry out feasibility and market potential study of new business models leveraging in prosumers and new digital ecosystems.	//	Onboarding, compliance with GDPR and measures to tackle plagiarism issues	Imec-SMIT, KUL	Open Access/ Copyright
ER3.1	Conceptualization of prosumer business models	Know-how	WP3	Design of feasible business models on a theoretical basis based on the role of "prosumers" in the sector	Imminent	No resources	IMEC-SMIT	Open Access/ Copyright
ER3.2	Know-how on the legal advice provided to the conceptualization of prosumer business models	Know-how	WP3	Know-how based on the legal implications of the Möbius Creator and player	Imminent	No resources	KUL	Open access
ER3.4	Know-how on the copyright Implications of Prosumer Business Models	Know-how	WP3	Explore the copyright implications of the prosumer business models developed within the framework of the Möbius Project	1 year	Publishing the results on scientific papers or sectorial journals	KUL, FEP	Open access

ER4	Möbius book prototype set of software tools	Software	WP4	Set of software tools that enable the production and consumption of cross-media immersive book experiences. The exploitation of SWs can be independent.	2 years	Marketing, sales, onboarding, IT support, product dev and UX/UI design and implementation, legal.	IN2, EUT	Copyright (for the IN2 components)
ER4.1	Möbius Creator Toolkit	Software	WP4	Allow the creation of interactive media-rich digital mobius books.	2 years	Marketing, sales, onboarding, IT support, product dev and UX/UI design and implementation, legal.	IN2	Copyright
ER4.2	Legal advice know-how on the foundations for the Möbius creator and player	Know-how	WP3	Assessing the Copyright implications of providing Möbius Creator and player	Imminent	No resources	KUL	Copyright<
ER4.3	Möbius Player	Software	WP4	Marketplace of Mobius Books and application that allows users to experience the immersive mobius book format	2 years	Marketing, sales, onboarding, IT support, product dev and UX/UI design and implementation, legal;	IN2	Copyright

ER4.4	Spatializer software	Software	WP4	It compiles a library of audios and improves the experience by changing the way the audio is transmitted from an audio into a surrounding space. It provides a sense of space to the reader.	6 months - 1 year	Personnel cost to develop the frontend. Still needs to be further developed.	EUT	Copyright
ER4.5	Alignment tool	Software SDK	WP4	Enhance the reading experience and support the reading activity. Words are illuminated at the same time that audio, so that the reader can followed them.	1 year	Not needed.	EUT	Copyright
ER4.6	User validation know-how with targeted end-users (e.g., experience with the PAN network)	Know-how	WP4	Know-how based on the validation of the functionalities of the Möbius creator toolkit with end-users. Potential creation of multi-modal books.	Imminent	Commercial resources.	KKW, IN2	Consortium

ER5	Möbius Immersive Book Box and experimental and cross-media productions based on a literary work for individual and social consumption	Product	WP5	Demonstrating cross-media and immersive book experiences for individual and social consumption.	1 year	Not needed.	Bookabook, KKW	Copyright
ER5.1	Adaptation of the text L'Influenza del Blue	Literary work	WP5	Translating and adapting an Italian publishing success that, as a dystonic fantasy that immerses the reader in an imaginary world, lends itself well to conversion to other media	Imminent	Not needed.	Bookabook	Copyright
ER5.2	Möbius Immersive Mobile Book Box and VR productions	Product	WP5	These productions allow the reader to experience new forms of relationship and encounters with a book, enjoying an original multimedia format. The	Imminent	Transport costs to move the mobile book box. Integration to current shows (night tour).	KKW	Copyright
ER5.3	3 immersive productions	Product	WP5	Immersive that will be organised in the KKW space and will be shown during the immersive night tours during the next year and perhaps beyond	Imminent	Not needed.	KKW	Copyright

ER6	Scientific publications on Möbius innovations	Know-how	WP2, WP3	Dissemination of project results and insights based on the innovative potential of the Möbius developments. Content addressing the following fields of interest: immersive media experience, legal advice, impact assessment methodology, prosumer business models and prosumer engagement	//	Not needed.	Imec-SMIT, DEN, KUL	Copyright
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Table 12: STEP 1: List of exploitable results

12.3 IPR Management - Step 2

Within the context of Task 6.2, involving all participating partners, the management of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) plays a pivotal role in ensuring the transparent, fair, and sustainable exploitation of project results.

One of the primary objectives of Task 6.2 is to systematically collect and analyze information about all project outputs, including unexpected ones, with a keen focus on their innovation and exploitation potential. This step is crucial to identify the intellectual property (IP) that may arise during the project's course and to determine its value and strategic importance, as determining the IP ownerships and facilitating the exploitation agreement necessary for the results.

As already included in deliverable D6.2, IP is a valuable asset that confers the right to entities to exclude others from the use of their creations or establish conditions on its exploitation.

When it comes to IP, we may differentiate the **background** brought to the project by partners and the **foreground**, the IP generated during the project. The Möbius Consortium Agreement (CA) contains all the relevant information referring to the partners' background and the Specific **limitations and/or conditions for implementation** (*Article 25.2 Grant Agreement*) and specific **limitations and/or conditions for exploitation** (*Article 25.3 Grant Agreement*). According to Table 3, 8 out of the 11 Möbius partners are bringing background to the project as agreed in the CA.

Partner	Previous Background (X= Yes)
Eurecat	X
IMEC	X
DEN	
IN2	X
MVB	X
BOOKABOOK	X
ENoLL	
FMWC	X
FEP	X
KKW	X
KU LEUVEN	

Table 13: Partners bringing background to the project

Next, to delve into the limitations for the implementation and exploitation of the background included in the CA, several tables focusing individually on the 8 partners will be included.

Eurecat		
Background	Limitations for implementation	Limitations for exploitation
Sfëar: Set of tools for 3D and binaural audio production.	Fundació Eurecat makes available Project relevant Background as needed for the implementation of the Project on a free basis.	Access to this background will be provided under fair and reasonable conditions.
SOFA Panner: Software tool to enable positioning audio sources in binaural productions.		
Contropedia: Interactive platform for exploring controversies in articles from MediaWiki powered platforms.		

Table 14: Eurecat – Background (CA)

IMEC		
Background	Limitations for implementation	Limitations for exploitation
Living lab framework: key methodology that aims to improve he design, development and adoption of future products or services by involving stakeholders throughout the whole innovation cycle. https://smit.vub.ac.be/expertise/living-labs	Access Rights to Background Needed for the performance of the own work of a Party under the Project shall be granted on a royalty-free basis	Access Rights to Background if Needed or Exploitation of a Party's own Results, shall be granted on Fair and Reasonable conditions.

Table 15: IMEC – Background (CA)

IN2		
Background	Limitations for implementation	Limitations for exploitation
<p>MyMeedia: Flexible media management and publishing platform. It includes a web-based authoring environment for the creation of mixed-media stories, a web-based application for the creation and management of content hubs and a series of dashboards for the visualisation of data and content metadata. The platform also contains modules for content analysis, enrichment and automatic annotation, content aggregation, indexing, syndication and publishing in 3rd party website or applications.</p>	<p>IN2 makes available Project relevant Background as needed for the implementation of the Project on a free basis.</p>	<p>Access to this background will be provided under fair and reasonable conditions.</p>
<p>Tellit: A web-based application for managing and re-using social media and web content alongside audiovisual content.</p>		

Table 16: IN2 – Background (CA)

MVB		
Background	Limitations for implementation	Limitations for exploitation
<p>Standardization of metadata and exchange formats within the publishing sector</p>	<p>MVB makes available Project relevant Background as needed for the implementation of the Project on a free basis.</p>	<p>Access to this background will be provided under fair and reasonable conditions.</p>

Expertise in user-centric digital product development methods		
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Table 17: MVB – Background (CA)

BOOKABOOK		
Background	Limitations for implementation	Limitations for exploitation
English market/language publishing rights and multimedia rights of “L’influenza del blu”.	Bookabook makes available Project relevant Background as needed for the implementation.	Access to this background will be provided under fair and reasonable conditions.
Strategy and best practices for crowdsourcing/crowdfunding publishing workflow		

Table 18: Bookabook – Background (CA)

FMWC		
Background	Limitations for implementation	Limitations for exploitation
Laboratory 5G: In our offices we have a laboratory with coverage of 5G NSA, LTE-M i NBloT by Telefonica	FMWC makes available Project relevant Background as needed for the implementation of the Project on a free basis.	FMWC makes available Project relevant Background as needed for the implementation and exploitation of the Project on a free basis ticket for the partners and the exhibition capabilities that are possible to showcase the project. Access to this background will be provided under fair and reasonable conditions.
Mentoring to SMEs: We offer a technological support service for companies that are interested in migrating their products to new networks capabilities.		

<p>5G Areas: 5G Barcelona has created different laboratories across Catalonia with infrastructure for test beds. As an example, a satellite unite for connectivity will be deployed in Lleida during 2021.</p>		
<p>Mobile World Congress: FMWC participates every year with a booth</p>		

Table 19: FMWC – Background (CA)

FEP		
Background	Limitations for implementation	Limitations for exploitation
<p>Know-how about the publishing sector.</p>	<p>EP makes available Project relevant Background as needed for the implementation of the Project on a free basis.</p>	<p>Access to this background will be provided under fair and reasonable conditions.</p>

Table 20: FEP – Background (CA)

KKW		
Background	Limitations for implementation	Limitations for exploitation
<p>Space to show immersive multimedia shows to a broad public audience and competence to design and produce such shows with an artistic ambition</p>	<p>Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig GmbH makes available Project relevant Background as needed for the implementation of the Project on a free basis.</p>	<p>Access to this background will be provided under fair and reasonable conditions.</p>

Table 21: KKW – Background (CA)

Based on the T6.2 work, the table below shows the Background (B) and Foreground (F) claims by project partners, collected from one-to-one interviews and in some cases, in meeting with more than 1 partner.

In terms of the **IPR** for the foreground generated, partners have identified **copyright** as the most suitable protection to safeguard their intellectual property generated. **Copyright** applies normally to literary and artistic works such as music, books, paintings, but also to computer programs (software), databases, etc. In addition, the **open access** has been considered in case of publications and some tools, which will be shared to the scientific community. The table below collects the naming and category of the Exploitable Result (ER), the IP claims (Foreground/Background), the description of the exploitation planned (that will be detailed in the Step 3 for the Key Exploitable Results) and the IPR protection that will be applied.

Individual IP claims tables for all partners have been included in Annex I.

N	ER	Category	WPs	IP CLAIMS	Foreseen exploitable results	Description of the exploitation planned	Owners	IPR foreseen protection
ER1	Möbius framework and methodologies	Methodology / toolkit	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	B, F	Internal Use/ Research Services	It will be applied to achieve streamlining meaningful, fair and sustainable cooperation with prosumers and cross-sectoral stakeholders through publishing value chains, including empirical assessment of social, economic and technological impacts.	FMWC, imec-SMIT, DEN, ENOLL, MVB, EUT	Copyright
ER1.1	Main evidence based on the Impact assessment of the Möbius KER	Know-how	WP2	F	Internal Use	This study will be internally used to understand how Mobius proposition and innovation impacts on the publishing sector.	DEN	Open access
ER1.2	Impact assessment methodology	Methodology / toolkit	WP2	F	Research Services	DEN will use the knowledge and the methodology for impact assessment to increase its competences and skills. The aim will be to further develop the framework to assess innovation in the publishing sector within EU funding projects or with other private funding.	DEN	Open access
ER1.3	Protocols for the workshops carried out to validate the project results	Procedure	WP5	B,F	Internal Use	It can be applied as a comparative analysis considering different setups and participants: online involvement of participants, cross-country workshops, etc	ENOLL, IMEC-Smit, FMWC	No IPR protection applied
ER1.4	User requirements know-how as a baseline for immersive reading developments	Methodology / Know-how	WP2, WP5	F	Research Services	The user requirements gathered during the workshops with end-users could help technology developers in new immersive reading tools	IMEC-SMIT	Open access

ER1.5	Knowledge on Möbius system requirements and relevant use-cases	Know-how	WP2	F	Internal Use	The developed skills and experimental issues will create meaningful systems for living labs	IN2	Copyright
ER1.6	Know-how on managing dissemination and communication activities in the publishing sector	Procedure	WP6	B,F	Services	This know-how can be useful to facilitate the creation of impact by the FMWC in other European projects	FMWC	No IPR protection applied
ER1.7	Long Term Roadmap / Business Plan Methodology	Know-How	WP6	B,F	Internal use	Use for building business activities and as a foundation for developing detailed planning after completing the Möbius project; The acquired know-how and methodology can be utilized for additional products.	MVB / EURECAT	Copyright
E1.7.1	Innovation workshops methodology oriented to business models		WP6	B,F	Internal Use	Foundation for potential establishment of business activities after project completion; The acquired know-how and methodology can be used for further products.	MVB	Copyright
E1.7.2	Exploitation and IPR management methodology		WP6	B,F	Internal Use	Basis for establishing joint venture business activities between the partners; The acquired know-how and methodology can be leveraged for additional products.	EURECAT	Copyright
ER2	Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT)	Toolkit	WP3	F	Commercialisation		IN2, EUT, imec-SMIT, FEP, MVB	Copyright
ER2.1	Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT) - Fan-fiction community metrics	Framework, Code	WP3	F	Licencing	The code will be licenced with a quite low, nearly symbolic price, since the aim of EUT is not as much profit as reasearch and development	EUT	Open-Source Code, copyright (publications)
ER 2.2	User Experience and applicability to the publishing sector	Know-how	WP3	F	Internal use	Internally used it will increase of the possibility of the PIT to be relevant in the publishing sector	FEP, MVB	No IPR protection applied

ER2.3	Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT) - Software/User interface (frontend and backend) for community metrics visualization	Software	WP3	F	Commercialisation	Commercial exploitation - Saas	IN2	Copyright
ER3	Möbius prosumer business models	Know-how	WP3	B,F	Research Services		Imec-SMIT, KUL	Open Access/ Copyright
ER3.1	Conceptualization of prosumer business models	Know-how	WP3	F	Research Services	Further R&D Projects, consultancy services	IMEC-SMIT	Open Access/ Copyright
ER3.2	Know-how on the legal advice provided to the conceptualization of prosumer business models	Know-how	WP3	B, F	Research Services	Further R&D Projects, consultancy services	KUL	Open access
ER3.4	Know-how on the copyright Implications of Prosumer Business Models	Know-how	WP3	B,F	Research Services	Further R&D Projects, consultancy services	KUL, FEP	Open access
ER4	Möbius book prototype set of software tools	Software	WP4	F	Commercialisation		IN2, EUT	Copyright (for the IN2 components)
ER4.1	Möbius Creator Toolkit	Software	WP4	F	Commercialisation	Commercial exploitation - Monthly subscription-based model with a freemium tear.	IN2	Copyright
ER4.2	Legal advice know-how on the foundations for the Möbius creator and player	Know-how	WP3	F	Internal Use	Further R&D Projects, consultancy services	KUL	Copyright
ER4.3	Möbius Player	Software	WP4	F	Commercialisation	Commercial exploitation - Freemium model for the player. Personalised functionality (like Library, Favourites, Comments) only for registered users (see subscription model for Creator)	IN2	Copyright

ER4.4	Spatializer software	Software	WP4	F	Licencing	The software will be licenced with a quite low, nearly symbolic price, since the aim of EUT is not as much profit as reasearch and development	EUT	Copyright
ER4.5	Alignment tool	Software SDK	WP4	F	Licencing	The software will be licenced with a quite low, nearly symbolic price, since the aim of EUT is not as much profit as reasearch and development	EUT	Copyright
ER4.6	User validation know-how with targeted end-users (e.g., experience with the PAN network)	Know-how	WP4	F	Internal Use	no exploitation planned	KKW, IN2	Consortium
ER5	Möbius Immersive Book Box and experimental and cross-media productions based on a literary work for individual and social consumption	Product	WP5		Commercialisation	Described bellow	Bookabook, KKW	Copyright
ER5.1	Adaptation of the text L`Influenza del Blue	Literary work	WP5	F	Licencing	Royalties will be charged for the use of the book in the immersive shows of KKW	Bookabook	Copyright

ER5.2	Möbius Immersive Mobile Book Box and VR productions	Product	WP5	F	Commercialisation	<p>The multimedia immersive shows will be presented in several modes:</p> <p>a.) Regular public presentations in the Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig in the next years in special regular program blocks and festivals (eg Leipzig book fair, Bright Festival)</p> <p>b.) Presentation of the show in other immersive venues in Europe and beyond (eg KKW has connections to sites in Italy, Spain, Portugal, Canada) and the shows could be adapted to their sites</p> <p>c.) Presentation of the MIB to be circulated in EUROPE for presentations eg on Book Fairs, on Book Reading festivals, meetings of author communities, schools, and even shopping centers.</p> <p>A business model is developed for renting the show content and the MIB separately. Royalties will be charged for the use of the book in the immersive shows of KKW</p>	KKW/Bookabook	Exploitation agreement between KKW and Book a Book to make sure the Intellectual Property rights are respected and royalties are paid in case of commercial presentations.
ER5.3	3 immersive productions	Product	WP5	F	Commercialisation	(Same as above)	KKW/Bookabook	Copyright
ER6	Scientific know-how generated on Möbius innovations	Know-how	WP2, WP3	F	Research Services	Dissemination	Imec-SMIT, DEN, KUL	Copyright

12.4 Möbius Key Exploitable Results (KERs) - Step 3

The Key Exploitable Results (KER) of the project are those considered to be the project outcomes with more **immediate and business impact**. In the case of Möbius, the KERs included below were agreed among all the project partners during the different exploitation workshops organised. They are considered to fulfill the following criteria: time-to-market lower than 1 year and high commercialization potential, moreover, they are tangible outcomes of the project that can have a direct impact on the market.

The tables below include the exploitation roadmaps for the different KERs. These tables aim at collecting partners' input regarding aspects related to the market (current trends, competitors), to the same result (differential value, problem and solution) and the forecasted impact generated (early adopters, sectors of application, long-term sustainability, etc.). Thus, the table is structured in KER's description, KER's market positioning, KER's market strategy and KER's IPR status.

12.4.1 ER5. Möbius Immersive Book Production and experimental and cross-media productions based on a literary work for individual and social consumption

KER's description	
Problem / Need identified	The publishing world has experimented with new forms of enjoyment of publishing content to a lesser extent than other cultural sectors, it was time to fill the gap. We have produced an innovative multimedia immersive show on two books which can be shown in three modes: a) in a large-scale immersive hall in Leipzig (site specific) and after adaptation in other similar locations, b) in a Mobile Immersive Box which can be brought to other locations, c) in VR-devices for demonstration purposes
Solution or innovation proposed / detailed description of the result	The immersive experience in general and the multimedia book allow the reader to experience new forms of relationship and encounters with the book. And at the same time, they allow content to meet new readers who are more attentive to multimedia experiences.
KER's market positioning	

<p>Current technological solutions available in the market (state-of-the-art)</p>	<p>The publishing market has mainly focused on digital books and audio books, leaving out the new potential of multimedia and immersive experiences. Our approach is highly innovative</p>
<p>Level of innovation introduced compared to existing products</p>	<p>The developed product is designed to be fully immersive and multimedia, unlike other publishing products that merely replicate through other media the content of the book. To make it available to visitors we have a version for large scale immersive shows in specialized venues and a mobile medium sized version (5mx 5m) which can be sent to interested locations</p>
<p>What makes the solution unique? (Unique Value Proposition). What is the competitive advantage of the result?</p>	<p>The fact that it is not a mere adaptation, but a completely new product designed from the beginning for an immersive experience. The immersive show is an artistic production in its own right</p>
<p>Key Competitors / Agents doing similar productions (mention names)</p>	<p>Developers of storytelling-driven immersive shows may be potential competitors. However, being well connected in the scene of immersive shows we only know of one production on book a story outside of Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig (Culture Espace, France with Alice in Wonderland). Kunstkraftwerk has a larger track record with 4 productions on book tales by now</p>
<p>Explain any potential technical barrier</p>	<p>At present, the technology used needs instrumentation that is not particularly complex, however the production of content requires experienced immersive artists and sound designers.</p>
<p>Explain any potential market barriers in the uptake of the technologies</p>	<p>The market barrier is the availability of large-scale immersive venues or of venues for presenting the MIB. The network of partners is developing in Europe.</p>
<p>Explain any social or cultural barriers that can influence the success of the result</p>	<p>Readers are at the same time users of other media content; there is no such thing as a reader who only reads books. This creates a strong demand for innovation that the book world has not yet been able to meet. However, once available in a city there is a great willingness and interest for immersive experience. Visitor numbers in Europe range from 30.000 to 1 million per year per venue.</p>
<p>Legal, normative or ethical requirements to be considered (need for)</p>	<p>None</p>

authorisations, compliance with standards, norms, specifications, etc).	
Potential customers and sectors of application - geographical location, typology of targeted end-users, etc.	<p>Several application scenarios can be anticipated:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a.) visit to the large venue in Leipzig b.) visit of the mobile immersive box on various locations like book fairs and some events outside the publishing world like conferences and festivals c.) educational presentations in public spaces and shopping malls
KER's market strategy	
Business model (how will it be monetized, replicated, etc.)	<p>We will present the multimedia immersive shows in several modes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a.) Regular public presentations in the Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig in the next years in special regular program blocks and festivals (e.g. Leipzig book fair, Bright Festival) b.) Presentation of the show in other immersive venues in Europe and beyond (e.g. KKW has connections to sites in Italy, Spain, Portugal, Canada) and the shows could be adapted to their sites c.) Presentation of the MIB to be circulated in EUROPE for presentations e.g. on Book Fairs, on Book Reading festivals, meetings of author communities, schools, and even shopping centers. <p>A business model is developed for renting the show content and the MIB separately</p>
Early adopters – List of initial clients	<p>We will start in Leipzig with attracting audience in regular events and will spread to the region (there is interest for immersive shows in shopping malls). We will also offer the shows to other venues contacted by the MÖBIUS partners (e.g. Milan, Barcelona, Brussels, etc.)</p>
Go to market approach (how to reach out early adopters) - what partner will commercialize?	<p>We will primarily follow two roads: 1.) offer the shows to other immersive Venues in Europe and beyond for rent; 2.) offer the shows in the MIB for non-specialist venues in Europe. KKW will be the partner responsible for commercialization</p>
Time-to-market (in years)	<p>We will begin in Spring 2024</p>

Investment needed after the project end to continue exploiting the result (in numbers)	No special investment needed
KER's IPR status	
Main owner/s of the result	Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig (KKW) has the exclusive rights from the immersive artist and the composer for the productions. KKW also owns the MIB. KKW will make an agreement with Book a Book regarding royalties of the book "Influence of Blue" which they published.
Other partners involved in developing the result	Book a Book
Other partners involved in commercialising the result	None
IPR strategy (have you protected, or will you protect this result? How? When? Will you carry out an exploitation agreement among the involved entities?)	Exploitation agreement between KKW and Book a Book to make sure the Intellectual Property rights are respected, and royalties are paid in case of commercial presentations.

Table 22: KER 1. Möbius Immersive Book Production and experimental and cross-media productions based on a literary work for individual and social consumption

12.4.1 ER4.2. Mobius Creator Toolkit

KER's description	
Problem / Need identified	Book reading, a leisure activity that requires time and concentration, is competing nowadays with an overwhelming entertainment offer brought about by digital technologies. The eBook share in the book market is growing, though steadily. The same digital technologies that are enabling consumer behaviour and change of habits (towards more subscription-based Video-on-Demand services) might be the key to captivating, again, the readers. Furthermore, the consumer is no longer a passive entity. The traditional frontiers between vendors and customers in media markets are blurring. Therefore, the times call for an offer to the prosumer phenomenon as a key aspect for business

	<p>competitiveness. Thus, the need was identified for a prosumer focused platform that allows for the creation of digital interactive and immersive tools that can enable the reading experience to compete with the popular mobile audiovisual content.</p>
<p>Solution or innovation proposed / detailed description of the result</p>	<p>Answering the need for a more immersive book experience that can be accessible to prosumers, the Creator Toolkit is built as a web-application and allows a user to assemble a Möbius book, which can then be viewed with the Möbius Player. The author creating a Möbius book can sprinkle within the digital text of a chapter several multimedia elements that can then be experienced by the reader based on their preferences. Most importantly, the author can add 3D audio to accompany the reading experience. A dedicated interface, called "the Spatializer", enables the author to align recorded audio narration to the actual text of a chapter. Sound effects and music can be added as well, and using the Spatializer's interface the author defines from where in the 3D space the sound will be coming from. In this way the reading experience can be enhanced with an immersive audioscape.</p>
<p>KER's market positioning</p>	
<p>Current technological solutions available in the market (state-of-the-art)</p>	<p>Platforms for production, creative feedback and discovery of digital books enjoy a scale unheard of in the paper era. On the one hand, there are communities like Fandom in which fans coordinate themselves to co-create wiki-powered guides. On the other hand, communities such as Wattpad, Fanfiction, Archive of Our Own (AO3), and specific communities from Reddit about fanfiction phenomena that go a step beyond elaboration by sharing and discussing alternative media content to canonical content. On the other hand, self-publishing has become more accessible, with aspiring</p>

	<p>authors being able to see their works as eBooks or print without a major financial investment by leveraging the services players such as Amazon (see more in the section Key-competitors).</p> <p>At the same time immersive technologies are becoming more commonplace, in part because of the emergence of XR (from AR to VR) for personal use, in professional settings or even in common experiences (e.g. museum installations). 3D audio has become more commonplace as well, becoming available to premium on-demand content providers (e.g. Netflix).</p>
<p>Level of innovation introduced compared to existing products</p>	<p>The Möbius creator enables users to create immersive digital reading experiences that go well beyond the capabilities that eBooks currently allow for.</p>
<p>What makes the solution unique? (Unique Value Proposition). What is the competitive advantage of the result?</p>	<p>The Möbius Creator Toolkit is a web-based application empowering authors to craft Möbius books that transcend traditional storytelling. Users can seamlessly assemble multimedia elements, providing readers with an interactive and immersive journey through words and sounds. Notably, the Möbius Book embraces 3D audio to augment the experience.</p>
<p>Key Competitors / Agents doing similar productions (mention names)</p>	<p>Currently in the market there are several offers for prosumers. Internationally, one notable player on the market is Wattpad, a free community of writers and readers; other important players focus on fanfiction, like AO3 Archive of Our Own or Fanfiction.net. There are also national initiatives which usually focus on supporting aspiring writers with community feedback, like Megustaescribir in Spain, or crowdsourcing new works, like Bookabook in Italy. All the solutions mentioned above focus on enabling writers to create new stories and books in the traditional text format and do not allow the inclusion of</p>

	<p>immersive elements in the books.</p> <p>There are also several solutions on the market for the self-publishing of eBooks, usually in EPUB format, either owned by large players (e.g. Amazon’s Kindle Direct Publishing, Apple Books for Authors, Barnes & Noble Press, the Books Partner Center for Google Play Books and Rakuten’s Kobo Writing Life.) or enabled by small providers (e.g. Leanpub, Gumroad).</p>
Explain any potential technical barrier	<p>The Möbius book format extends the existing EPUB standard format. This means that existing eReaders that implement EPUB are not able to correctly render Möbius books created with the Creator’s Toolkit. While EUT is following the new developments of the EPUB standard, standardization activities require significant timespans, and it is not certain when a new version of EPUB that supports multiple audio tracks will be published.</p>
Explain any potential market barriers in the uptake of the technologies	<p>The uptake of the Möbius creator toolkit is predicated by the successful creation of an initial community of users. This is a very difficult challenge that only a few platforms manage to overcome, and it usually requires a mix of financial resources invested, committed team to evangelize and promote, “stickiness” of the solution, and opportune timing to enter the market.</p>
Explain any social or cultural barriers that can influence the success of the result	<p>Prosumers might already find themselves too embedded in a certain existing community and will not leave that one or have the necessary time to join another.</p>
Legal, normative or ethical requirements to be considered (need for authorisations, compliance with standards, norms, specifications, etc).	<p>The Möbius team is aware of the new European copyright regulations as well as the new regulation for content controls on platforms. These are described at length in D3.5.</p>

<p>Potential customers and sectors of application - geographical location, typology of targeted end-users, etc.</p>	<p>Target groups identified: Professional and amateur writers People working in the educational and cultural sector Publishing houses Sectors: Creative sector, amateur/hobby writers Cultural, artistic and educational Creative and publishing sector</p>
<p>KER's market strategy</p>	
<p>Business model (how will it be monetized, replicated, etc.)</p>	<p>Monthly subscription-based model with a freemium tear. For more details, please consult D6.5</p>
<p>Early adopters – List of initial clients</p>	<p>Prosumers</p>
<p>Go to market approach (how to reach out early adopters) - what partner will commercialize?</p>	<p>IN2 will lead the commercialisation effort. After the end of the project a series of steps will need to be taken in order to prepare for the launch of the product. For more details, please consult D6.5</p>
<p>Time-to-market (in years)</p>	<p>1</p>
<p>Investment needed after the project end to continue exploiting the result (in numbers)</p>	<p>~ 370.000 EUR. Breakdown: 50000 EUR initial marketing budget; 1 FTE (70k EUR yearly) for customer acquisition, 0.5 FTE (35k EUR yearly) marketing specialist, 0.5 FTE (35k EUR yearly) community and content manager, 1 FTE (70k EUR yearly) ICT developer, 30k yearly for hosting and operation costs, 30K consulting and licensing.</p>
<p>KER's IPR status</p>	
<p>Main owner/s of the result</p>	<p>IN2</p>
<p>Other partners involved in developing the result</p>	<p>EUT (Spatialiser 3D audio tool)</p>
<p>Other partners involved in commercialising the result</p>	<p>-</p>
<p>IPR strategy (have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When? Will you carry out an exploitation)</p>	<p>The code will be licensed with a quite low, nearly symbolic price, since the aim of EUT</p>

agreement among the involved entities?)	is not as much profit as research and development.
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Table 23: KER 2. Mobius Creator Toolkit

14.4.3. ER3 Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT)

KER's description	
Problem / Need identified	Publishers need data and tools to extract meaningful information from it in order to understand reader trends and be able to better plan printing and distribution as well as scouting of new titles. Availability of data is, however, restricted or too expensive as there are disconnects in the value-chain.
Solution or innovation proposed / detailed description of the result	The prosumer intelligence toolkit (PIT) is a data analysis and visualisation platform. It allows users to get a quick overview but also explore deeply large data sets about prosumers (books and authors). The PIT can be adapted to work with own data streams from publishers or other purchased/collected prosumer data. By default, it uses the data collected from the AO3 platform.
KER's market positioning	
Current technological solutions available in the market (state-of-the-art)	Big data analysis is usually performed in-house by data scientists. Visualisations are usually developed on demand (e.g. as consulting). There are also several SaaS companies specialised in data visualisation based on generic data (e.g. Tableau); often though these use spreadsheets as databases and support only limited data analysis and search functionality.
Level of innovation introduced compared to existing products	Since data has been in recent years experienced a "gold rush", the field of solutions for visualisation is a crowded one. The most important innovation of the PIT relates to its customisation to prosumer

	publishing data which has its own unique characteristics.
What makes the solution unique? (Unique Value Proposition). What is the competitive advantage of the result?	The PIT is tailored to deal with prosumer data about books. All underlying data analysis modules are tailored for this, for e.g. to determine network connectivity of authors or predict success based on existing community response. The visualizations of the PIT are interactive.
Key Competitors / Agents doing similar productions (mention names)	As previously mentioned, competitors are only dealing with generic analysis and visualisation of data: <i>Tableau, ChartBlocks, Datawrapper, D3.js, Google Charts, FusionCharts.</i>
Explain any potential technical barrier	Completely unstructured data formats that requires significant “cleaning” before being used in the PIT
Explain any potential market barriers in the uptake of the technologies	Limited availability of prosumer data (i.e platform owners not sharing data or having pricing which is prohibitive)
Explain any social or cultural barriers that can influence the success of the result	Conservative nature of publishing sector which tends not to consider prosumers “serious writers” or don’t see them as valuable target audience.
Legal, normative or ethical requirements to be considered (need for authorisations, compliance with standards, norms, specifications, etc).	Processing large datasets of prosumer data has GDPR implications.
Potential customers and sectors of application - geographical location, typology of targeted end-users, etc.	Any type of publisher could be a potential customer. However, smaller niche publishers who target younger non-mainstream readers could be better suited (since for them the prosumer data would be more valuable)
KER’s market strategy	
Business model (how will it be monetized, replicated, etc.)	Different tiers. Off-the-shelf SaaS solution with monthly subscription for those interested in AO3 data only. Customised SaaS (B2B model), one-time set-up cost to integrate own data sources and yearly costs of subscription.

Early adopters – List of initial clients	Early adopters to be targeted are the publishers involved during the piloting activities.
Go to market approach (how to reach out early adopters) - what partner will commercialize?	IN2 will be the main partner commercializing the result. We plan to reach out to early adopters through direct contact (phone, email) and physical meetings during bookfairs (e.g. Frankfurt Bookfair 2024)
Time-to-market (in years)	0,5 years
Investment needed after the project end to continue exploiting the result (in numbers)	50000 EUR initial marketing budget. 1 FTE (70k EUR yearly) sales and marketing representative
KER's IPR status	
Main owner/s of the result	IN2, EUT
Other partners involved in developing the result	IMEC (testing)
Other partners involved in commercialising the result	-
IPR strategy (have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When? Will you carry out an exploitation agreement among the involved entities?)	Commercial agreements to be finalised after the project ends.

Table 24: KER 3. Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT)

14.4.2 ER4.3 Möbius player

KER's description	
Problem / Need identified	Immersive Mobius Books crafted with the Mobius Creator have a special format which includes multimedia elements and 3D audio. These require a dedicated player to provide the reader with the necessary interface to fully experience the Mobius Book.
Solution or innovation proposed / detailed description of the result	The Möbius Player is a responsive application designed to provide readers with a fully immersive and interactive experience.

	<p>Compatible with any device and operating system, Möbius Player ensures accessibility for a broad audience. When exploring Möbius books, readers encounter 3D audio, narrations, and multimedia elements that come to life, transforming the act of reading into an engaging adventure.</p> <p>Key Features of the Möbius Player:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsive Design: Möbius Player adapts to various devices and operating systems, ensuring a seamless reading experience across platforms. • 3D Audio Immersion: Upon opening a Möbius book, readers are immersed in voice narrations, sound effects, and music, enhancing the narrative and atmosphere. • User-Controlled Experience: Readers have the freedom to customise their experience by toggling different audio channels on or off, allowing for a personalised journey through the Möbius book. • Multimedia Integration: Interactive multimedia elements are seamlessly embedded within the text, providing readers with a dynamic and engaging encounter with the content. • Marketplace for Prosumers: Open marketplace for prosumers to showcase their Mobius Books; discover new authors and stories and save favourite titles to your library
KER's market positioning	
<p>Current technological solutions available in the market (state-of-the-art)</p>	<p>Current digital reading applications implement a user interface for browsing and visualising pdf and epub files. Most applications provide a page-by-page view of a document or book, with the ability to use a “page-less” view too, which optimises the number of words displayed based on the screen size and chosen font size. Few other</p>

	<p>reading options are generally available (e.g. dark mode).</p> <p>In contrast, most audio book players function as an audio playlist, which each chapter of the book being an individual track. The user is only able to hear the narration but not read the actual text of the chapter.</p>
Level of innovation introduced compared to existing products	At the moment there is no other player capable of providing the full user experience of a Mobius Book.
What makes the solution unique? (Unique Value Proposition). What is the competitive advantage of the result?	Möbius Book represents a paradigm shift in how we engage with digital literature, offering both authors and readers a new dimension of storytelling. Embrace the future of immersive reading with Möbius Book
Key Competitors / Agents doing similar productions (mention names)	There are countless applications (free or otherwise) that allow users to read pdf or epub files. For audio books the main players are the big platforms like Apple, Amazon Audible, and Spotify, with smaller startups targeting different niches (e.g. Blinkst)
Explain any potential technical barrier	The Mobius Player is built as a responsive web-application so that it can be accessible on all devices and operating systems. However, this means it is not findable in the mobile app stores (like Apple, Google Play). Users can still make the Player an app shortcut on their phone (and make it behave like any other native app), but this requires a minimal gadget know-how.
Explain any potential market barriers in the uptake of the technologies	The Mobius Player is only relevant when bundled with the Mobius Creator and is predicted by the popularity of the Creator with prosumers to craft immersive Mobius Books. Similar to the barrier of the Creator, the uptake is dependent on the successful creation of an initial community of users. This is a very difficult challenge that only a few platforms manage to overcome, and it usually requires a mix of financial resources

	invested, committed team to evangelize and promote, “stickiness” of the solution, and opportune timing to enter the market.
Explain any social or cultural barriers that can influence the success of the result	In certain markets like Germany, people still tend to consider reading a purely physical activity, preferring the physical book experience over the digital one.
Legal, normative or ethical requirements to be considered (need for authorisations, compliance with standards, norms, specifications, etc).	The Möbius team is well aware of the new European copyright regulations as well as the new regulation for content controls on platforms. These are described at length in D3.5.
Potential customers and sectors of application - geographical location, typology of targeted end-users, etc.	<p>Target groups identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional and amateur writers • People working in the educational and cultural sector • Publishing houses <p>Sectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creative sector, amateur/hobby writers • Cultural, artistic and educational • Creative and publishing sector
KER's market strategy	
Business model (how will it be monetized, replicated, etc.)	The Player will be bundled with the Creator. Freemium model for the player. Personalised functionality (like Library, Favourites, Comments) only for registered users (see subscription model for Creator)
Early adopters – List of initial clients	(Young) readers
Go to market approach (how to reach out early adopters) - what partner will commercialize?	IN2 will lead the commercialisation effort. After the end of the project a series of steps will need to be taken in order to prepare for the launch of the product. The Player will be

	bundled with the Creator. For more details, please consult D6.5
Time-to-market (in years)	1
Investment needed after the project end to continue exploiting the result (in numbers)	Investment estimate of Creator (~370.000 EUR) covers the Player investment (as it is a bundled product).
KER's IPR status	
Main owner/s of the result	IN2
Other partners involved in developing the result	-
Other partners involved in commercialising the result	-
IPR strategy (have you protected or will you protect this result? How? When? Will you carry out an exploitation agreement among the involved entities?)	We plan to release the Player as open source.

Table 25: KER 4. Möbius Player

12.4.4 Benchmark analysis of similar solutions to the Möbius Book

The innovative applications of the Möbius Book, integrating the player, the creator app and the prosumer intelligence toolkit (PIT) are complete solutions that contribute to providing immersive reading experiences for readers, the empowerment of content creators and the offering of relevant insights for publishers. Moreover, the Möbius book has adopted a user-centric approach that has been validated through real-life testing sessions.

In this subsection, some potential 'substitutes' of the Möbius book have been included. The benchmark analysis formulated is taking into account the different functionalities of the Möbius book and compare them.

Description of the solution/company	Möbius differentiation strategy
Inkitt: A platform that allows writers to publish their stories and get feedback from readers. Inkitt also uses data analysis to identify potential bestsellers and offers publishing deals to authors.	While Inkitt provides data analysis insights, the Möbius PIT also can do that and in addition, the Möbius player transforms stories into immersive experiences.
Wattpad: A website and app that lets users read and write stories across various genres. Wattpad also has a fanfiction section, where users can create and consume stories based	The Möbius book takes a step forward and provides an interactive reading experience and provides analytical insights to creators (data-driven approach).

<p>on their favorite fandoms. Wattpad also partners with publishers and media companies to adapt stories into books, movies, and TV shows.</p>	
<p>Storytel: A subscription service that offers unlimited access to audiobooks and e-books. Storytel also has a feature called Storytel Original, where they produce exclusive audio series in different languages and genres.</p>	<p>Beyond creating audio series, the Möbius book through the 3d sound system can provide more valuable immersive experiences to the users and provide data insights to the publishers.</p>
<p>IR books by library ideas commercializes directly immersive books (audio and video), individual books cost 39.95\$.</p>	<p>The Möbius book does not include video but its stance is more oriented towards the community of prosumers, allowing different creators to generate its own stories and receive guidance and data through its platform.</p>
<p>Book2look: It creates samples of books, the so called “Biblets”, customized by the publishers and with the possibility of adding audio and video clips as well as shop links. It can be shared in the relevant Social Networks and can recommend books also via SMS and WhatsApp. In addition to this it is linked to BookNet and delivers data about visualization and use of the Biblets through a dashboard. Booksellers and Bloggers can also make use of the Biblets personalizing them and using them for marketing purposes. In some countries it is possible to test it for free for a limited period of time.</p>	<p>Book2look is conceived as a mere marketing tool: one can only create samples of books and enrich them, but not the book itself as an immersive experience. Also, the data dashboard delivers information related exclusively to the produced samples and its views/ clicks or where they were shared, but not about large communities or trends as Möbius does.</p>
<p>Neuronale Bücher/ Intelligentes E-Book: German project still in development. It means to offer individualized, personalized, regionalized, and context-related content as well as target group-specific offers are tailored precisely to meet customer needs and requirements, continuously evolving and co-created by the customer. Each customer essentially will configure their own book. The digital 'product' is no longer replicable in the traditional sense, as it changes with each interaction and generates numerous variations over time. It's not only about the technology but also about a completely new, digital, and scalable business model for publishers, media houses, and educational institutions. Publishers, in particular, regain control over the content and thus their business model.</p>	<p>Even though both projects have a similar orientation and perspectives, Möbius is more focused on fiction and prosumers while the Neuronale Bücher Project is on specialist and technical Literature. On the other hand, the concept of prosumers will not be explored in the German project, nor data will be gathered from open communities. Also, the immersive audio features of Möbius are not in the scope of Neuronale Bücher.</p>

<p>The main contributors are E-nnovalytics with a technology partner from Vienna (ebcont) and a software partner for the publishing industry from Munich (SiteFusion), who have been driving the digitization of the publishing industry for many years (including THIEME, Klett, Cornelsen).</p> <p>The consortium financed the development of the prototype with funding from public sources (the German Zentralen Innovationsprogramm Mittelstand (ZIM)). And they are in contact with several publishers who are willing to invest in and support this development as investors and partners.</p>	
<p>Audible Original in Dolby Atmos (Amazon) Dolby Atmos uses the latest spatial audio technology from Dolby Studios, to provide Audible customers with an immersive sound experience.</p>	<p>The user cannot create the audio content himself as it is possible in the Möbius Creator.</p>

Table 26: Benchmark analysis of similar solutions

13. Final Considerations

In reflection to the Communication and Dissemination plan that has been executed throughout the project, some best practices, highlights, and lessons learnt have been detected. On the one hand, some **best practices** have been implementing the **Open Call** communication campaign, which effectively engaged the Möbius target audience through one-on-one messaging, helping to connect on a personal level. Thus, this **one-on-one messaging** that has been deployed through LinkedIn thanks to a tool called Scrab.in has been used to increase the number of followers on social media, attract attendees to online and offline organised events, find **prosumers** and **publishers**.

Möbius also leveraged on **cross-dissemination** with stakeholders, expanding its reach and fostering valuable partnerships, such as with the other ICT-44 funded projects (the so-called sibling projects), as well as the project's supportive partners. Moreover, FMWC started creating more video content to adapt the communication strategy to the constant changes of the sector. Maintaining a strong and consistent brand identity through the website, social media banners, and marketing materials such as tote bags, notebooks, and stickers enhanced the project's recognition and memorability among its audience.

Among the project highlights, the Open Call Awards Ceremony, the policy events, the Möbius Closing Event at the Frankfurt Book Fair 2023 organised by MVB and the Mobile World

Congress 2024 by Mobile World Capital Barcelona, and the Fantastic Adventure night organised by the KKW were significant milestones. These events showcased the project's achievements and provided valuable opportunities for engagement, networking, and knowledge sharing. They underscored the power of **well-executed events** in driving the project's goals forward.

Considering the **lessons learned** from this campaign, it's clear that **paid campaigns** played a crucial role in expanding the social media reach and engagement. Having a clear target audience and well-defined objectives from the outset is essential in guiding the communication efforts effectively. Thus, FMWC acknowledges that the **prosumers' concept** was difficult to work with in terms of communication since people identified as such very few. Also, emphasising the importance of working closely with partners, sibling projects, and supportive partners has been crucial to maximise impact and resources. FMWC commitment to **consistency in messaging, branding, and identity-building** demonstrated that it is an indispensable element in strengthening the project's **brand recognition and impact**.

From an exploitation perspective, the contributions of tasks T6.2 have been included both to D6.4 and D6.5 and aims at sharing and potentiating the application of Möbius results to the targeted market and the research areas. Möbius has generated a total of **6 main Exploitable Results** encompassing **24 sub-results**. The typology of ERs has been wide: 6 SWs, 3 products, 2 procedures, 11 know-how, 6 methodologies and/or toolkits, 1 literary work and 1 code framework.

Throughout the **exploitation methodology**, starting with the identification of exploitable results and the characterisation of the overview table and the further development of exploitation roadmaps for KERs based on the prioritisation done, many individual meetings and also **3 business clinic workshops** were held. During these meeting, exploitation managers did not only focus on the technical results, as they are by themselves relevant in a R&D project, but also, it focused on non-technical ERs. This double focus aimed at integrating and exposing the interdisciplinary synergies that happened in Möbius and providing the same value to the results generated addressing for instance, impact assessment methodology as equally relevant than the immersive experiences.

Thus, from an exploitation perspective the results have been diverse and interdisciplinary as the exploitation routes that will be followed. The emphasis given also to the project's scientific contributions stands out the contribution of Möbius to the cultural and creative industries body of knowledge.

After circulating a **feedback survey** among the Möbius partners about the WP6. The overall think the communication and dissemination of the project throughout the three years has been great, which includes project activities and partners promotion to increase project visibility and impact in social media, fairs, and events:

“The dissemination initiative as part of the work package has facilitated a broader reach and engagement. By using various channels of communication, e.g. social media, newsletters, and scientific publications, etc., it has been possible to reach a diverse audience. From our side,

e.g. in referring to the website when inviting stakeholders to participate in evaluation activities, we deem the support of this work package to have been crucial.” – Anonymous partner.

Finally, it is convenient to list of **five communication and dissemination recommendations** for future projects in a similar sector. For Möbius, it was extremely helpful to increase the visibility of the project by having the open call at the beginning of the project, but it would have been much appreciated to have some more spread throughout the project. Following with the suggestions, building a **community** in a niche sector is easier with FSTP mechanisms. As another recommendation, since finding new spaces and ways to test and improve the applications and experiences has been rather difficult, having even more direct connections with publishers would have been helpful. A possible way to ensure feedback would be connecting with university degrees or master's students.

14. Annex I: Individual IP claims

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1.2 IP Claims - Bookabook

N	ER	Category	WPs	IP CLAIMS	Foreseen exploitable results	Description of the exploitation planned	Owners and % of ownership	Other partners involved	IPR foreseen protection
ER5	Möbius Immersive Book Box and experimental and cross-media productions based on a literary work for individual and social consumption	Product	WP5		Commercialisation	Described below		Bookabook, KKW	Copyright
ER5 .1	Adaptation of the text L'Influenza del Blue	Literary work	WP5	F	Licencing	Royalties will be charged for the use of the book in the immersive shows of KKW	Bookabook	Bookabook	Copyright

Tabella 1: IP Claims - Bookabook

1.3 IP Claims - IMEC

N	ER	Category	WPs	IP CLAIMS	Foreseen exploitable results	Description of the exploitation planned	Owners and % of ownership	Other partners involved	IPR foreseen protection
ER1	Möbius framework and methodologies	Methodology / toolkit	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	B, F	Internal Use/ Research Services	It will be applied to achieve streamlining meaningful, fair and sustainable cooperation with prosumers and cross-sectoral stakeholders through publishing value chains, including empirical assessment of social, economic and technological impacts.		FMWC, imec-SMIT, DEN, ENOLL, MVB, EUT	Copyright
ER1.3	Protocols for the workshops carried out to validate the project results	Procedure	WP5	B,F	Internal Use	It can be applied as a comparative analysis considering different setups and participants: online involvement of participants, cross-country workshops, etc		ENOLL, IMEC-Smit, FMWC	No IPR protection applied
ER1.4	User requirements know-how as a baseline for immersive reading developments	Methodology / Know-how	WP2, WP5	F	Research Services	The user requirements gathered during the workshops with end-users could help technology developers in new immersive reading tools		IMEC-SMIT	Open access
ER2	Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT)	Toolkit	WP3	F	Commercialisation	//		IN2, EUT, imec-SMIT, FEP, MVB	Copyright
ER3	Möbius prosumer business models	Know-how	WP3	B,F	Research Services	//		Imec-SMIT, KUL	Open Access/ Copyright
ER3.1	Conceptualization of prosumer business models	Know-how	WP3	F	Research Services	Further R&D Projects, consultancy services		IMEC-SMIT	Open Access/ Copyright

ER6	Scientific know-how generated on Möbius innovations	Know-how	WP2, WP3	F	Research Services	Dissemination		Imec-SMIT, DEN, KUL	Copyright
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Tabelle 2: IP Claims - IMEC

1.4 IP Claims - Eurecat

N	ER	Category	WPs	IP CLAIMS	Foreseen exploitable results	Description of the exploitation planned	Owners and % of ownership	Other partners involved	IPR foreseen protection
ER1	Möbius framework and methodologies	Methodology / toolkit	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	B, F	Internal Use/ Research Services	It will be applied to achieve streamlining meaningful, fair and sustainable cooperation with prosumers and cross-sectoral stakeholders through publishing value chains, including empirical assessment of social, economic and technological impacts.		FMWC, imec-SMIT, DEN, ENOLL, MVB, EUT	Copyright
ER1.7	Long Term Roadmap / Business Plan Methodology	Know-How	WP6	B, F	Internal use	Use for building business activities and as a foundation for developing detailed planning after completing the Möbius project; The acquired know-how and methodology can be utilized for additional products.		MVB / EURECAT	Copyright (?)
E1.7.2	Exploitation and IPR management methodology		WP6	B, F	Internal Use	Basis for establishing joint venture business activities between the partners; The acquired know-how and methodology can be leveraged for additional products.		EURECAT	

ER2	Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT)	Toolkit	WP3	F	Commercialisation			IN2, EUT, imec-SMIT, FEP, MVB	Copyright
ER2.1	Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT) - Fan-fiction community metrics	Framework, Code	WP3	F	Licencing	The code will be licenced with a quite low, nearly symbolic price, since the aim of EUT is not as much profit as reasearch and development		EUT	Open Source Code, copyright (publications)
ER4	Möbius book prototype set of software tools	Software	WP4	F (Möbius Creator Toolkit)	Licencing	The software will be licenced with a quite low, nearly symbolic price, since the aim of EUT is not as much profit as reasearch and development		IN2, EUT	Copyright (for the IN2 components)
ER4.4	Spatializer software	Software	WP4	F	Licencing	The software will be licenced with a quite low, nearly symbolic price, since the aim of EUT is not as much profit as reasearch and development		EUT	Copyright
ER4.5	Alignment tool	Software SDK	WP4	F	Licencing	The software will be licenced with a quite low, nearly symbolic price, since the aim of EUT is not as much profit as reasearch and development		EUT	Copyright

Tabelle 3: IP Claims - Eurecat

1.5 IP Claims - Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig

N	ER	Category	WPs	IP CLAIMS	Foreseen exploitable results	Description of the exploitation planned	Partners involved	IPR foreseen protection
ER4.6	User validation know-how with targeted end-users (e.g., experience with the PAN network)	Know-how	WP4	F	Internal Use	No exploitation planned	KKW, IN2	Consortium
ER5	Möbius Immersive Book Box and experimental and cross-media productions based on a literary work for individual and social consumption	Product	WP5		Commercialisation	Described below	Bookabook, KKW	Copyright

ER5.2	Möbius Immersive Mobile Book Box and VR productions	Product	WP5	F	Commercialisation	<p>The multimedia immersive shows will be presented in several modes:</p> <p>a.) Regular public presentations in the Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig in the next years in special regular program blocks and festivals (e.g. Leipzig book fair, Bright Festival)</p> <p>b.) Presentation of the show in other immersive venues in Europe and beyond (e.g. KKW has connections to sites in Italy, Spain, Portugal, Canada) and the shows could be adapted to their sites</p> <p>c.) Presentation of the MIB to be circulated in EUROPE for presentations e.g. on Book Fairs, on Book Reading festivals, meetings of author communities, schools, and even shopping centers.</p> <p>A business model is developed for renting the show content and the MIB separately.</p>	KKW	Exploitation agreement between KKW and Book a Book to make sure the Intellectual Property rights are respected and royalties are paid in case of commercial presentations.
ER5.3	Three immersive productions	Product	WP5	F	Commercialisation	(Same as above)	KKW	Copyright

Tabelle 4: IP Claims - KKW

1.6 IP Claims - IN2

N	ER	Category	WPs	IP CLAIMS	Foreseen exploitable results	Description of the exploitation planned	Partners involved	IPR foreseen protection
ER1	Möbius framework and methodologies	Methodology / toolkit	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	B, F	Internal Use/ Research Services	It will be applied to achieve streamlining meaningful, fair and sustainable cooperation with prosumers and cross-sectoral stakeholders through publishing value chains, including empirical assessment of social, economic and technological impacts.	FMWC, imec-SMIT, DEN, ENOLL, MVB, EUT	Copyright
ER1.5	Knowledge on Möbius system requirements and relevant use-cases	Know-how	WP2	F	Internal Use	The developed skills and experimental issues will create meaningful systems for living labs	IN2	Copyright
ER2	Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT)	Toolkit	WP3	F	Commercialisation	Different tiers. Off-the-shelf SaaS solution with monthly subscription for those interested in AO3 data only. Customised SaaS (B2B model), one-time set-up cost to integrate own data sources and yearly costs of subscription.	IN2, EUT, imec-SMIT, FEP, MVB	Copyright
ER2.3	Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT) - Software/User interface (frontend and backend) for community metrics visualization	Software	WP3	F	Commercialisation	Commercial exploitation - Saas	IN2	Copyright
ER4	Möbius book prototype set of software tools	Software	WP4	F	Commercialisation	No exploitation foreseen	IN2, EUT	Copyright (for the IN2 components)

ER4.1	Mobius Creator Toolkit	Software	WP4	F	Commercialisation	Monthly subscription-based model with a freemium tear.	IN2	Copyright
ER4.3	Mobius Player	Software	WP4	F	Commercialisation	The Player will be bundled with the Creator. Freemium model for the player. Personalised functionality (like Library, Favourites, Comments) only for registered users (see subscription model for Creator)	IN2	Copyright
ER4.6	User validation know-how with targeted end-users (e.g., experience with the PAN network)	Know-how	WP4	F	Internal Use	Commercial exploitation - Freemium model for the player. Personalised functionality (like Library, Favourites, Comments) only for registered users (see subscription model for Creator)	KKW, IN2	Consortium
ER4.5	Alignment tool	Software SDK	WP4			//	EUT	Copyright
ER4.6	User validation know-how with targeted end-users (e.g., experience with the PAN network)	Know-how	WP4			//	KKW, IN2	Consortium

Tabelle 5: IP Claims - IN2

1.6 IP Claims - ENoLL

N	ER	Category	WPs	IP CLAIMS	Foreseen exploitable results	Description of the exploitation planned	Partners involved	IPR foreseen protection
ER1	Möbius framework and methodologies	Methodology / toolkit	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	B, F	Internal Use/ Research Services	It will be applied to achieve streamlining meaningful, fair and sustainable cooperation with prosumers and cross-sectoral stakeholders through publishing value chains, including empirical assessment of social, economic and technological impacts.	FMWC, imec-SMIT, DEN, ENOLL, MVB, EUT	Copyright
ER1.3	Protocols for the workshops carried out to validate the project results	Procedure	WP5	B,F	Internal Use	It can be applied as a comparative analysis considering different setups and participants: online involvement of participants, cross-country workshops, etc	ENOLL, IMEC-Smit, FMWC	No IPR protection applied

Tabelle 6: IP Claims - ENoLL

1.7 IP Claims - DEN Institute

N	ER	Category	WPs	IP CLAIMS	Foreseen exploitable results	Description of the exploitation planned	Partners involved	IPR foreseen protection
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ER1	Möbius framework and methodologies	Methodology / toolkit	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	B, F	Internal Use/ Research Services	It will be applied to achieve streamlining meaningful, fair and sustainable cooperation with prosumers and cross-sectoral stakeholders through publishing value chains, including empirical assessment of social, economic and technological impacts.	FMWC, imec-SMIT, DEN, ENOLL, MVB, EUT	Copyright
ER1.1	Main evidences based on the Impact assessment of the Möbius KER	Know-how	WP2	F	Internal Use	This study will be internally used to understand how Mobius proposition and innovation impacts on the publishing sector.	DEN	Open access
ER1.2	Impact assessment methodology	Methodology / toolkit	WP2	F	Research Services	DEN will use the knowledge and the methodology for impact assessment to increase its competences and skills. The aim will be to further develop the framework to assess innovation in the publishing sector within EU funding projects or with other private funding.	DEN	Open access
ER6	Scientific know-how generated on Möbius innovations	Know-how	WP2, WP3	F	Research Services	Thanks to the know-how acquired during the project, DEN will try to increase its position in the publishing sector developing services for sectorial stakeholders to support cross sectorial scalability and impact assessment analysis.	Imec-SMIT, DEN, KUL	Copyright

Tabelle 7: IP Claims - DEN Institute

1.8 IP Claims - Mobile World Capital

N	ER	Category	WPs	IP CLAIMS	Foreseen exploitable results	Description of the exploitation planned	Partners involved	IPR foreseen protection
ER1	Möbius framework and methodologies	Methodology / toolkit	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	B, F	Internal Use/ Research Services	It will be applied to achieve streamlining meaningful, fair and sustainable cooperation with prosumers and cross-sectoral stakeholders through publishing value chains, including empirical assessment of social, economic and technological impacts.	FMWC, imec-SMIT, DEN, ENOLL, MVB, EUT	Copyright
ER1.3	Protocols for the workshops carried out to validate the project results	Procedure	WP5	B,F	Internal Use	It can be applied as a comparative analysis considering different setups and participants: online involvement of participants, cross-country workshops, etc	ENOLL, IMEC-Smit, FMWC	No IPR protection applied
ER1.6	Know-how on managing dissemination and communication activities in the publishing sector	Procedure	WP6	B,F	Services	This know-how can be useful to facilitate the creation of impact by the FMWC in other European projects	FMWC	No IPR protection applied

Table 8: IP Claims - Mobile World Capital

1.9 IP Claims - MVB

N	ER	Category	WPs	IP CLAIMS	Foreseen exploitable results	Description of the exploitation planned	Partners involved	IPR foreseen protection
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ER1	Möbius framework and methodologies	Methodology / toolkit	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	B, F	Internal Use/ Research Services	It will be applied to achieve streamlining meaningful, fair and sustainable cooperation with prosumers and cross-sectoral stakeholders through publishing value chains, including empirical assessment of social, economic and technological impacts.	FMWC, imec-SMIT, DEN, ENOLL, MVB, EUT	Copyright
ER1.7	Long Term Roadmap / Business Plan Methodology	Know-How	WP6	B,F	Internal use	Use for building business activities and as a foundation for developing detailed planning after completing the Möbius project; The acquired know-how and methodology can be utilized for additional products.	MVB / EURECAT	Copyright (?)
E1.7.1	Innovation workshops methodology oriented to business models		WP6	B,F	Internal Use	Foundation for potential establishment of business activities after project completion; The acquired know-how and methodology can be used for further products.	MVB	
ER2	Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT)	Toolkit	WP3	F	Commercialisation	No exploitation foreseen	IN2, EUT, imec-SMIT, FEP, MVB	Copyright
ER 2.2	User Experience and applicability to the publishing sector	Know-how	WP3	F	Internal use	Internally used it will increase of the possibility of the PIT to be relevant in the publishing sector	FEP, MVB	No IPR protection applied

Tabelle 9: IP Claims - MVB

1.10 IP Claims - KU LEUVEN

N	ER	Category	WPs	IP CLAIMS	Foreseen exploitable results	Description of the exploitation planned	Partners involved	IPR foreseen protection
ER3	Möbius prosumer business models	Know-how	WP3	B,F	Research Services	IMEC will use the result on further R&D projects and the provision of services to new clients.	Imec-SMIT, KUL	Open Access/ Copyright
ER3.2	Know-how on the legal advice provided to the conceptualization of prosumer business models	Know-how	WP3	B, F	Research Services	No exploitation planned	KUL	Open access
ER3.4	Know-how on the copyright Implications of Prosumer Business Models	Know-how	WP3	B,F	Research Services	No exploitation planned	KUL, FEP	Open access
ER4.2	Legal advice know-how on the foundations for the Möbius creator and player	Know-how	WP3	F	Internal Use	No exploitation planned	KUL	Copyright
ER6	Scientific know-how generated on Möbius innovations	Know-how	WP2, WP3	F	Research Services	Dissemination	Imec-SMIT, DEN, KUL	Copyright

Tabelle 10: IP Claims - KU Leuven

1.11 IP Claims - Federation of European Publishers

N	ER	Category	WPs	IP CLAIMS	Foreseen exploitable results	Description of the exploitation planned	Partners involved	IPR foreseen protection
ER2	Möbius Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT)	Toolkit	WP3	F	Commercialisation	No exploitation planned	IN2, EUT, imec-SMIT, FEP, MVB	Copyright
ER 2.2	User Experience and applicability to the publishing sector	Know-how	WP3	F	Internal use	Internally used it will increase of the possibility of the PIT to be relevant in the publishing sector	FEP, MVB	No IPR protection applied
ER3.4	Know-how on the copyright Implications of Prosumer Business Models	Know-how	WP3	B,F	Research Services	No exploitation planned	KUL, FEP	Open access

Tabelle 11: IP Claims - FEP

